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B A C H E L O R A R B E I T

**Centralizing Monoids
on a Three-Element Set**

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CONTENTS

Contents

1	Introduction	2
2	Preliminaries	3
2.1	Basic notation	3
2.2	Closure operators	4
2.3	Galois connections	6
2.4	Lattices	7
3	Formal concept analysis	8
3.1	Formal contexts	8
3.2	Concept lattices	11
3.3	Standard context	13
4	Centralizing monoids on finite sets	17
4.1	Commutation and centralizers	17
4.2	Formal context of commutation	18
4.3	Centralizing monoids	20
4.4	Witnesses for centralizing monoids	21
5	Witness-complete sets	26
6	Centralizing monoids on a three-element set	31
7	Appendix	34
7.1	C++ code	34
7.2	Object and attribute abbreviations	44
7.3	Output context	46
7.4	Standard context	51
7.5	Centralizing monoids and corresponding witnesses	53

1 Introduction

The endomorphism monoid of a universal algebra consists of all endofunctions which commute with every operation of the algebra. Hence, studying commutation for multi-variable functions, which is a generalization of commutation for unary functions, is crucial for understanding endomorphism monoids. For a set of operations F , the centralizer is defined as the set of functions which commute with every operation in F . The unary part of a centralizer is called a centralizing monoid. For a universal algebra, the unary part of the centralizer of its set of fundamental operations is precisely the endomorphism monoid of the algebra. The set of operations of the algebra is called a witness for this monoid.

In this thesis, we will study centralizing monoids on finite sets and, in particular, we consider the case of a three-element set. By using formal concept analysis and computing the formal context of unary centralizers, we will determine all 192 centralizing monoids and corresponding witnesses on a three-element set.

In a series of papers, Machida and Rosenberg extensively studied centralizing monoids on a three-element set. Their endeavour to determine all centralizing monoids on a three-element set started in [8], where they presented three maximal centralizing monoids. In [6], Machida and Rosenberg introduced the witness lemma, which will be used throughout this thesis to construct witnesses for centralizing monoids. They were able to determine all 10 maximal centralizing monoids and corresponding singleton witnesses on a three-element set in [7]. A strategy how to obtain all centralizing monoids on a three-element set by using the 10 maximal centralizing monoids is presented in [5]. In that paper, it is reported that following this strategy one obtains a total of 192 centralizing monoids. The 192 monoids are not listed, and the paper contains very little information on how these monoids were actually computed. However, Machida and Rosenberg published the slightly extended version [9] of the previously mentioned paper [5]. This extended version includes a table containing all 192 centralizing monoids but no list of witnesses is given. Although it is described how to apply the method from [5] for a few examples, details are still missing. Further results on centralizing monoids have been published since then, but none related to determining every centralizing monoid on a three-element set.

The goal of this thesis is to verify the number of centralizing monoids on a three-element set, which was presented in [5], by using a different approach and obtaining the same result. Furthermore, we will also list a witness for every centralizing monoid. Since the unary part of a centralizer is always a centralizing monoid, giving a witness provides a simple method to verify

2 PRELIMINARIES

that the listed monoids are indeed centralizing monoids. It only has to be checked that the unary part of the centralizer of the witness coincides with the corresponding monoid.

In Section 2, basic notation will be clarified. Additionally, an introduction to closure operators, Galois connections and lattices is given. In Section 3, formal contexts and concept lattices are defined and studied. Centralizing monoids, witnesses and the context of commutation are presented in Section 4. Section 5 introduces the notion of a witness-complete set, and a sufficiently small finite witness-complete set is constructed. Our strategy for obtaining every centralizing monoid on a three-element set is outlined in Section 6. Appendix 7 contains the full C++ code which was used to compute a subcontext of the formal context of unary centralizers having an isomorphic concept lattice. This subcontext and the corresponding standard context are also given. Furthermore, the appendix contains a complete list of all centralizing monoids on a three-element set, including witnesses.

2 Preliminaries

In this section, we will clarify the basic notation which will be used throughout this thesis. The fundamental notation in this thesis is mainly based on [1]. Furthermore, we will give an introduction to closure operators and Galois connections. There is also a subsection about lattices which is necessary before defining the standard context in Subsection 3.3.

2.1 Basic notation

We write $\mathbb{N} = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$ for the set of all natural numbers and the set of all positive integers is denoted by $\mathbb{N}_+$. The von Neumann model of natural numbers will be used, i.e., $n = \{0, \dots, n-1\}$. We denote the cardinality of a set by $|A|$. For any set A , the power set is denoted by $\mathcal{P}(A)$.

The set of all functions from A to B will be denoted by B^A . A function $f \in A^I$ can also be represented as $(f_i)_{i \in I}$, where $f_i = f(i)$. For a function $f \in B^A$ and $X \subseteq A$, we denote the image $\{f(x) \mid x \in X\}$ by $f[X]$. For functions $f: A \rightarrow B$ and $g: B \rightarrow C$, we will symbolize the composition of g and f as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} g \circ f: A &\rightarrow C \\ a &\mapsto g(f(a)). \end{aligned}$$

Given a natural number $n \in \mathbb{N}$, a tuple $x \in A^n$ is a function from the set $\{0, \dots, n-1\}$ to A which will officially be written as $x = (x_0, \dots, x_{n-1})$. Although technically incorrect, indexing from 1 to n will often be used to

2 PRELIMINARIES

improve readability, i.e., we will sometimes pretend that $x \in A^n$ is a map from $\{1, \dots, n\}$ to A and denote it by $x = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$. Understanding tuples as functions enables us to compose them with other maps. Given sets A, B, I , a tuple $x \in A^n$ and maps $f: A \rightarrow B$, $\beta: I \rightarrow n$, we obtain that $f \circ x = (f(x_1), \dots, f(x_n)) \in B^n$ and $x \circ \beta = (x_{\beta(i)})_{i \in I} \in A^I$.

2.2 Closure operators

Before treating Galois connections, we will define and examine closure operators. Although closure operators are not necessary to define Galois connections, this approach is useful because Galois connections between certain sets induce a pair of canonical closure operators.

Definition 2.1. For a set M , a function $\varphi: \mathcal{P}(M) \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(M)$ is called a *closure operator* on M if it fulfills the following conditions for all subsets $X, Y \subseteq M$:

- (i) $X \subseteq \varphi(X)$.
- (ii) $X \subseteq Y \Rightarrow \varphi(X) \subseteq \varphi(Y)$.
- (iii) $\varphi(\varphi(X)) = \varphi(X)$.

We often write φX for $\varphi(X)$. The set φX is called the *closure* of X .

Definition 2.2. A set $\mathfrak{C} \subseteq \mathcal{P}(M)$ is called a *closure system* on the set M if $M \in \mathfrak{C}$ and it is closed under intersections:

$$\forall \mathfrak{B} \subseteq \mathfrak{C}: \bigcap \mathfrak{B} \in \mathfrak{C}.$$

As the similar names might indicate, there is a direct connection between closure operators and closure systems:

Theorem 2.3 ([4, Theorem 1]). *Let $\mathfrak{C}$ be a closure system on M and φ be a closure operator on M . The set*

$$\mathfrak{C}_\varphi := \{\varphi X : X \in \mathcal{P}(M)\}$$

is a closure system on M . Conversely, the following function defines a closure operator on M :

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_{\mathfrak{C}}: \mathcal{P}(M) &\rightarrow \mathcal{P}(M) \\ X &\mapsto \bigcap \{A \in \mathfrak{C} : X \subseteq A\}. \end{aligned}$$

Additionally, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{C}_{\varphi_{\mathfrak{C}}} &= \mathfrak{C} \\ \varphi_{\mathfrak{C}_\varphi} &= \varphi. \end{aligned}$$

2 PRELIMINARIES

Proof. Firstly, we prove that $\mathfrak{C}_\varphi$ is a closure system. Let $\mathfrak{B} \subseteq \mathfrak{C}_\varphi$. The function φ is a closure operator, therefore we know that $\bigcap \mathfrak{B} \subseteq \varphi(\bigcap \mathfrak{B})$. For every set $A \in \mathfrak{B} \subseteq \mathfrak{C}_\varphi$ there exists a set $X \subseteq M$ such that $A = \varphi(X)$. This leads to the following equation:

$$A = \varphi(X) = \varphi(\varphi(X)) = \varphi(A).$$

Because of this equation and property (ii) of closure operators, it follows that

$$\varphi(\bigcap \mathfrak{B}) \subseteq \varphi(A) = A \text{ for every } A \in \mathfrak{B}.$$

This implies $\varphi(\bigcap \mathfrak{B}) \subseteq \bigcap \mathfrak{B}$. Finally, we have

$$\bigcap \mathfrak{B} = \varphi(\bigcap \mathfrak{B}) \in \{\varphi X : X \in \mathcal{P}(M)\} = \mathfrak{C}_\varphi.$$

Now we will show that $\varphi_{\mathfrak{C}}$ is a closure operator:

(i) It obviously holds that $X \subseteq \bigcap \{A \in \mathfrak{C} : X \subseteq A\} = \varphi_{\mathfrak{C}}(X)$.

(ii) For arbitrary $X, Y \subseteq M$, the inclusion $X \subseteq Y$ implies

$$\{A \in \mathfrak{C} : X \subseteq A\} \supseteq \{A \in \mathfrak{C} : Y \subseteq A\}.$$

Hence, we have that

$$\varphi_{\mathfrak{C}}(X) = \bigcap \{A \in \mathfrak{C} : X \subseteq A\} \subseteq \bigcap \{A \in \mathfrak{C} : Y \subseteq A\} = \varphi_{\mathfrak{C}}(Y).$$

(iii) $\varphi_{\mathfrak{C}}(X) \subseteq \varphi_{\mathfrak{C}}(\varphi_{\mathfrak{C}}(X))$ follows immediately from (i). For any set $A' \in \mathfrak{C}$ we have, again by (i), that

$$X \subseteq A' \Leftrightarrow \varphi_{\mathfrak{C}}(X) = \bigcap \{A \in \mathfrak{C} : X \subseteq A\} \subseteq A'.$$

The idempotency of $\varphi_{\mathfrak{C}}$ follows directly from this equivalence:

$$\varphi_{\mathfrak{C}}(\varphi_{\mathfrak{C}}(X)) = \bigcap \{A \in \mathfrak{C} : \varphi_{\mathfrak{C}}(X) \subseteq A\} = \bigcap \{A \in \mathfrak{C} : X \subseteq A\} = \varphi_{\mathfrak{C}}(X).$$

For $A \in \mathfrak{C}_\varphi$ and $X \subseteq M$, the inclusion $X \subseteq A$ is equivalent to $\varphi(X) \subseteq A$. Hence, we get the following equation:

$$\varphi_{\mathfrak{C}_\varphi}(X) = \bigcap \{A \in \mathfrak{C}_\varphi : X \subseteq A\} = \bigcap \{A \in \mathfrak{C}_\varphi : \varphi(X) \subseteq A\} = \varphi(X).$$

Additionally, we can show $\mathfrak{C} = \mathfrak{C}_{\varphi_{\mathfrak{C}}}$ by using the fact that $\mathfrak{C}$ is closed under intersections:

$$X \in \mathfrak{C} \Leftrightarrow X = \bigcap \{A \in \mathfrak{C} : X \subseteq A\} \Leftrightarrow X = \varphi_{\mathfrak{C}}(X) \Leftrightarrow X \in \mathfrak{C}_{\varphi_{\mathfrak{C}}}. \quad \square$$

2 PRELIMINARIES

Closure systems are very widespread throughout different areas of mathematics:

- For any topological space X , the set of all closed sets constitutes a closure system. The usual closure of a set defines a closure operator.
- For any algebra $\mathcal{A}$, the function which maps a subset $X \subseteq \mathcal{A}$ to the smallest subalgebra containing X is a closure operator. The set of all subalgebras is the corresponding closure system.
- The set of all equivalence relations on a set S constitutes a closure system.

2.3 Galois connections

Definition 2.4. Let $(P, \leq)$ and $(Q, \leq)$ be ordered sets and $\varphi: P \rightarrow Q$ and $\psi: Q \rightarrow P$ be maps between these ordered sets. The pair (φ, ψ) is called a *Galois connection* between the ordered sets $(P, \leq)$ and $(Q, \leq)$ if it fulfills the following conditions:

- (i) $p_1 \leq p_2 \Rightarrow \varphi(p_1) \geq \varphi(p_2)$ for $p_1, p_2 \in P$.
- (ii) $q_1 \leq q_2 \Rightarrow \psi(q_1) \geq \psi(q_2)$ for $q_1, q_2 \in Q$.
- (iii) $p \leq \psi(\varphi(p))$ and $q \leq \varphi(\psi(q))$ for $p \in P, q \in Q$.

Lemma 2.5 ([4, Proposition 4]). *For ordered sets $(P, \leq)$ and $(Q, \leq)$, and maps $\varphi: P \rightarrow Q$ and $\psi: Q \rightarrow P$, the pair (φ, ψ) is a Galois connection if and only if*

$$\forall p \in P \forall q \in Q: p \leq \psi(q) \Leftrightarrow q \leq \varphi(p).$$

Proof. “ $\Rightarrow$ ”: Because of property (i) of Galois connections, $p \leq \psi(q)$ implies $\varphi(p) \geq \varphi(\psi(q))$. Using property (iii), it follows that

$$q \leq \varphi(\psi(q)) \leq \varphi(p).$$

The other direction can be proven analogously.

“ $\Leftarrow$ ”: Firstly, we will prove property (iii). Since $\varphi(p) \leq \varphi(p)$, we can deduce that $p \leq \psi(\varphi(p))$ by using $q = \varphi(p)$. Analogously, $q \leq \varphi(\psi(q))$ can be shown.

Because of property (iii), it holds that $p_1 \leq p_2$ implies $p_1 \leq p_2 \leq \psi(\varphi(p_2))$. We thus obtain that $\varphi(p_1) \geq \varphi(p_2)$ using $q = \varphi(p_2)$. Property (ii) follows symmetrically. $\square$

Lemma 2.6 ([4, Proposition 5]). *For a Galois connection (φ, ψ) , the following equations apply:*

$$\varphi = \varphi \circ \psi \circ \varphi \text{ and } \psi = \psi \circ \varphi \circ \psi.$$

2 PRELIMINARIES

Proof. For each $p \in P$, the inequality $\varphi(p) \leq \varphi(\psi(\varphi(p)))$ follows from property (iii) using $q = \varphi(p)$. Conversely, we also obtain $p \leq \psi(\varphi(p))$ from (iii). Property (i) of Galois connections now implies $\varphi(p) \geq \varphi(\psi(\varphi(p)))$. The second equation follows analogously. $\square$

For two sets M and N , we call a pair of functions (φ, ψ) a *Galois connection between M and N* if the pair (φ, ψ) is a Galois connection between $(\mathcal{P}(M), \subseteq)$ and $(\mathcal{P}(N), \subseteq)$. Galois connections between power sets are especially important because they canonically induce closure operators on M and N . In this case, we will often use the notation φA instead of $\varphi(A)$.

Proposition 2.7 ([4, Proposition 8]). *Let (φ, ψ) be a Galois connection between the sets M and N . The maps $A \mapsto \psi\varphi A$ and $B \mapsto \varphi\psi B$ are closure operators on M and N , respectively.*

Proof. We will only prove that $\psi \circ \varphi$ is a closure operator on M .

- (i) $X \subseteq Y \Rightarrow \varphi X \supseteq \varphi Y \Rightarrow \psi\varphi X \subseteq \psi\varphi Y$ for $X, Y \subseteq M$.
- (ii) $X \subseteq \psi\varphi X$ is fulfilled due to property (iii) of Galois connections.
- (iii) $\psi\varphi(\psi\varphi X) = (\psi \circ \varphi \circ \psi)(\varphi X) = \psi\varphi X$ holds because of Lemma 2.6.

Symmetrically, it can be proven that $\phi \circ \psi$ is a closure operator on N . $\square$

2.4 Lattices

Before defining formal contexts and concept lattices, we will clarify the notation regarding lattices in this subsection. A partially ordered set $(L, \leq)$ is called a *lattice* if the supremum $p \vee q$ and the infimum $p \wedge q$ exist for any two elements $p, q \in L$. A lattice is called *complete* if the supremum and infimum exist for any subset of L . The supremum of the set $\{p_i \in L \mid i \in I\}$ will be denoted by $\bigvee \{p_i \in L \mid i \in I\}$ or $\bigvee_{i \in I} p_i$. Dually, the infimum will be denoted by $\bigwedge \{p_i \in L \mid i \in I\}$ or $\bigwedge_{i \in I} p_i$.

An element p of a complete lattice L is called (*completely*) *supremum-irreducible* if it cannot be represented as the supremum of strictly smaller elements, i.e.,

$$p \neq \bigvee \{q \in L \mid q < p\}.$$

Similarly, p is called (*completely*) *infimum-irreducible* if it cannot be represented as the infimum of strictly larger elements. The set of all supremum-irreducible elements and the set of all infimum-irreducible elements of a complete lattice L are denoted by $J(L)$ and $M(L)$, respectively. A set $X \subseteq L$ is called *supremum-dense* in the lattice L if for every $p \in L$ it holds that

$$p = \bigvee \{m \in X \mid m \leq p\}.$$

3 FORMAL CONCEPT ANALYSIS

Symmetrically, the set $X \subseteq L$ is called *infimum-dense* if it satisfies

$$p = \bigwedge \{m \in X \mid m \geq p\}$$

for every $p \in L$.

Lemma 2.8 ([4, Proposition 2]). *In a finite lattice L , the set $J(L)$ is supremum-dense and the set $M(L)$ is infimum-dense.*

Note that every finite lattice is complete, and hence also well-founded.

Proof. We will use well-founded induction to prove that every $p \in L$ can be represented as the supremum of a subset of $J(L)$. Let $p \in L$ be such that

$$q = \bigvee \{x \in J(L) \mid x \leq q\} \text{ for every } q < p.$$

If $p \in J(L)$, it obviously holds that

$$p = \bigvee \{x \in J(L) \mid x \leq p\}.$$

If $p \notin J(L)$, we know that $p = \bigvee \{q \in L \mid q < p\} = \bigvee_{q < p} q$. Using the equation $q = \bigvee \{x \in J(L) \mid x \leq q\}$ for every $q < p$, we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} p &= \bigvee_{q < p} q \\ &= \bigvee_{q < p} \bigvee \{x \in J(L) \mid x \leq q\} \\ &\leq \bigvee \{x \in J(L) \mid \exists q < p: x \leq q\} \\ &= \bigvee \{x \in J(L) \mid x < p\} \\ &\leq p. \end{aligned}$$

We have shown that $J(L)$ is supremum-dense. Analogously, it can be shown that $M(L)$ is infimum-dense. $\square$

3 Formal concept analysis

This section is based on Sections 1.1 and 1.2 in [4] and Sections 1.2 and 1.3 in [3].

3.1 Formal contexts

Definition 3.1. A *formal context* $\mathbb{K} = (G, M, I)$ consists of two sets, G and M , and a binary relation $I \subseteq G \times M$. The elements of G are called the *objects* and the elements of M are called the *attributes* of the context $\mathbb{K}$. If an object $g \in G$ and an attribute $m \in M$ are in relation I , we will usually

3 FORMAL CONCEPT ANALYSIS

use the notation $g I m$ instead of $(g, m) \in I$ and read this as “the object g has the attribute m ”. We often omit the word “formal” in “formal context”.

For $H \subseteq G$ and $N \subseteq M$, we can form a *subcontext* $\mathbb{K}' = (H, N, I \cap (H \times N))$ of $\mathbb{K}$. Although it is technically incorrect, we will usually specify a subcontext without the intersection $\cap (H \times N)$, i.e., we will define a subcontext (H, N, I) and the restriction of I is implicitly given by the sets of objects and attributes.

A cross table can be useful to visualize a small finite formal context. The rows are headed by the object names and columns are headed by the attribute names. A cross in row g and column m indicates that the object g has the attribute m .

Definition 3.2. For a set of objects $A \subseteq G$, we define the set of their common attributes

$$A^\uparrow := \{m \in M \mid \forall g \in A: g I m\}.$$

Dually, for a set of attributes $B \subseteq M$ we define the set of all objects which have all attributes in B

$$B^\downarrow := \{g \in G \mid \forall m \in B: g I m\}.$$

The operators $\uparrow$ and $\downarrow$ are called the *derivation operators* of (G, M, I) . Usually, we will not distinguish the $\uparrow$ and $\downarrow$ operators and simply write A' and B' instead. Additionally, we will often use the notation A'' instead of $(A^\uparrow)^\downarrow$ and B'' instead of $(B^\downarrow)^\uparrow$. We will also use m' and g' as a short form for $\{m\}'$ and $\{g\}'$, respectively.

Proposition 3.3 ([4, Proposition 10]). *For a formal context (G, M, I) and subsets $A, A_1, A_2 \subseteq G$, the following facts hold:*

- (i) $A_1 \subseteq A_2 \Rightarrow A_1' \supseteq A_2'$.
- (ii) $A \subseteq A''$.
- (iii) $A' = A'''$.

Dually, for subsets $B, B_1, B_2 \subseteq M$ we have

- (i') $B_1 \subseteq B_2 \Rightarrow B_1' \supseteq B_2'$.
- (ii') $B \subseteq B''$.
- (iii') $B' = B'''$.

3 FORMAL CONCEPT ANALYSIS

Additionally, it holds that

$$(iv) \quad A \subseteq B' \Leftrightarrow B \subseteq A' \Leftrightarrow A \times B \subseteq I.$$

Proof. We will only prove the statements (i)-(iii) and (iv), the statements (i')-(iii') can be proven analogously to their counterparts.

- (i) Let $A_1 \subseteq A_2$. For $m \in A'_2$, we have $g I m$ for all $g \in A_2$ and thus in particular $g I m$ for all $g \in A_1$. Hence, we obtain that $m \in A'_1$.
- (ii) By definition, every $g \in A$ satisfies $g I m$ for all $m \in A'$. It immediately follows that $g \in \{h \in G \mid \forall m \in A': h I m\} = A''$.
- (iii) The inclusion $A' \subseteq A'''$ follows immediately by (ii'). Conversely, $A' \supseteq A'''$ follows from (i) because $A \subseteq A''$.
- (iv) By looking at the definitions, it becomes apparent that all of the statements in (iv) are equivalent to

$$\forall g \in A \forall m \in B: g I m. \quad \square$$

Corollary 3.4. *For a context (G, M, I) , the derivation operators form a Galois connection between G and M . The maps $A \mapsto A''$ and $B \mapsto B''$ are closure operators on G and M , respectively.*

Proof. In Proposition 3.3, we have already proven that the derivation operators satisfy the necessary conditions for a Galois connection. Furthermore, we have shown that every Galois connection between two sets canonically induces a closure operator on each set in Proposition 2.7. $\square$

Lemma 3.5 ([4, Proposition 11]). *Let $A_i \subseteq G$ and $B_i \subseteq M$ for $i \in I$. Then the following equations hold:*

$$\left(\bigcup_{i \in I} A_i \right)' = \bigcap_{i \in I} A'_i \quad \text{and} \quad \left(\bigcup_{i \in I} B_i \right)' = \bigcap_{i \in I} B'_i.$$

Proof. Clearly, we have

$$\begin{aligned} m \in \left(\bigcup_{i \in I} A_i \right)' &\Leftrightarrow \forall g \in \bigcup_{i \in I} A_i: g I m \\ &\Leftrightarrow \forall i \in I \forall g \in A_i: g I m \\ &\Leftrightarrow \forall i \in I: m \in A'_i \\ &\Leftrightarrow m \in \bigcap_{i \in I} A'_i. \end{aligned}$$

The second equation follows symmetrically. $\square$

3.2 Concept lattices

Definition 3.6. A *formal concept* of the context (G, M, I) is a pair (A, B) which satisfies

$$A \subseteq G, B \subseteq M, A' = B \text{ and } B' = A.$$

The set A is called the *extent* and the set B the *intent* of the concept (A, B) . Denote the set of all concepts of the context (G, M, I) by $\mathfrak{B}(G, M, I)$. We denote the set of all extents by $\mathfrak{E}(G, M, I)$ and the set of all intents by $\mathfrak{I}(G, M, I)$. We often omit the word “formal” in “formal concept”.

Note that every formal concept (A, B) can be written as (A, A') and (B', B) .

Proposition 3.7. *For any set of objects $A \subseteq G$, the following holds:*

- (i) *The pair (A'', A') is a formal concept.*
- (ii) *The set A is the extent of some concept if and only if $A'' = A$.*
- (iii) *The set A'' is the smallest extent containing A .*

Symmetric results hold for sets of attributes.

Proof. (i) We get $A''' = A'$ using Proposition 3.3.

- (ii) If $A'' = A$, then A is the extent of the concept $(A'', A') = (A, A')$. Let A be the extent of the concept (A, B) . From $A = B'$ and $B = A'$, we thus immediately obtain that $A = B' = A''$.
- (iii) Let (C, B) be a concept such that $A \subseteq C$. Using Proposition 3.3, we get $A' \supseteq C' = B$, and therefore also $A'' \subseteq B' = C$. $\square$

There is a natural hierarchy to order formal concepts:

Definition 3.8. Let (A_1, B_1) and (A_2, B_2) be formal concepts of some context (G, M, I) . We define the binary relation $\leq$ as follows:

$$(A_1, B_1) \leq (A_2, B_2) :\Leftrightarrow A_1 \subseteq A_2.$$

If $(A_1, B_1) \leq (A_2, B_2)$, then (A_1, B_1) is called a *subconcept* of (A_2, B_2) and (A_2, B_2) is called a *superconcept* of (A_1, B_1) . The set of all concepts of $\mathfrak{B}(G, M, I)$ ordered by the relation $\leq$ is called the *concept lattice* of the context (G, M, I) .

Note that for two concepts (A, B) and (A, C) , it follows directly from the definition that $B = A'$ and $C = A'$, hence $(A, B) = (A, C)$. We thus know that the intent of a concept is unique. The same holds for extents.

Lemma 3.9. *For formal concepts (A_1, B_1) and (A_2, B_2) of some context (G, M, I) , it holds that*

$$(A_1, B_1) \leq (A_2, B_2) \Leftrightarrow B_1 \supseteq B_2.$$

3 FORMAL CONCEPT ANALYSIS

Proof. The sets B_1 and B_2 are the intents of some concepts, therefore we get $B_1 = B_1''$ and $B_2 = B_2''$ by Proposition 3.7. Together with the implications

$$B_1 \supseteq B_2 \Rightarrow B_1' \subseteq B_2' \Rightarrow B_1'' \supseteq B_2'',$$

we get that $B_1 \supseteq B_2$ is equivalent to $B_1' \subseteq B_2'$. We thus obtain that

$$(A_1, B_1) \leq (A_2, B_2) \Leftrightarrow A_1 \subseteq A_2 \Leftrightarrow B_1' \subseteq B_2' \Leftrightarrow B_1 \supseteq B_2. \quad \square$$

Theorem 3.10 ([4, Theorem 3]). *The concept lattice $(\mathfrak{B}(G, M, I), \leq)$ is a complete lattice. For any set $\{(A_i, B_i) \in \mathfrak{B}(G, M, I) \mid i \in I\}$, the infimum and the supremum are given by*

$$\begin{aligned} \bigwedge_{i \in I} (A_i, B_i) &= \left(\bigcap_{i \in I} A_i, \left(\bigcup_{i \in I} B_i \right)'' \right). \\ \bigvee_{i \in I} (A_i, B_i) &= \left(\left(\bigcup_{i \in I} A_i \right)'', \bigcap_{i \in I} B_i \right). \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Firstly, note that $(\mathfrak{B}(G, M, I), \leq)$ is partially ordered because the relation $\subseteq$ is a partial order on $\mathcal{P}(G)$ and the extent of a concept is unique. Let $\{(A_i, B_i) \mid i \in I\} \subseteq \mathfrak{B}(G, M, I)$ be an arbitrary set. From $A_i = B_i'$, $B_i = A_i'$ and Lemma 3.5, we obtain the equations

$$\left(\bigcap_{i \in I} A_i, \left(\bigcup_{i \in I} B_i \right)'' \right) = \left(\bigcap_{i \in I} B_i', \left(\bigcup_{i \in I} B_i \right)'' \right) = \left(\left(\bigcup_{i \in I} B_i \right)', \left(\bigcup_{i \in I} B_i \right)'' \right),$$

and dually

$$\left(\left(\bigcup_{i \in I} A_i \right)'', \bigcap_{i \in I} B_i \right) = \left(\left(\bigcup_{i \in I} A_i \right)'', \bigcap_{i \in I} A_i' \right) = \left(\left(\bigcup_{i \in I} A_i \right)'', \left(\bigcup_{i \in I} A_i \right)' \right).$$

This means that they have the form (X', X'') and (Y'', Y') , respectively, and are therefore concepts due to Proposition 3.7 (i). It obviously holds for every $i \in I$ that

$$\left(\bigcap_{i \in I} A_i, \left(\bigcup_{i \in I} B_i \right)'' \right) \leq (A_i, B_i) \leq \left(\left(\bigcup_{i \in I} A_i \right)'', \bigcap_{i \in I} B_i \right).$$

Let $(C, D) \in \mathfrak{B}(G, M, I)$ be such that $(C, D) \leq (A_i, B_i)$ for all $i \in I$, i.e. $C \subseteq A_i$ for all $i \in I$. Consequently, we have $C \subseteq \bigcap_{i \in I} A_i$. We have now proven that $\{(A_i, B_i) \mid i \in I\}$ has an infimum in $\mathfrak{B}(G, M, I)$ and

$$\bigwedge_{i \in I} (A_i, B_i) = \left(\bigcap_{i \in I} A_i, \left(\bigcup_{i \in I} B_i \right)'' \right).$$

3 FORMAL CONCEPT ANALYSIS

Let $(C, D) \in \mathfrak{B}(G, M, I)$ be such that $(A_i, B_i) \leq (C, D)$ for all $i \in I$, i.e., $A_i \subseteq C$ for all $i \in I$. Hence, we get $\bigcup_{i \in I} A_i \subseteq C$. The inclusion $(\bigcup_{i \in I} A_i)'' \subseteq C$ follows by Proposition 3.7 (iii). We have shown that the supremum exists and

$$\bigvee_{i \in I} (A_i, B_i) = \left(\left(\bigcup_{i \in I} A_i \right)'', \bigcap_{i \in I} B_i \right). \quad \square$$

We recall that the set of all extents is denoted by $\mathfrak{E}(G, M, I)$ and the set of all intents by $\mathfrak{I}(G, M, I)$.

Proposition 3.11. *The lattices*

$$(\mathfrak{B}(G, M, I), \leq), (\mathfrak{E}(G, M, I), \subseteq) \text{ and } (\mathfrak{I}(G, M, I), \supseteq)$$

are isomorphic.

Proof. We define the function

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi: \mathfrak{E}(G, M, I) &\rightarrow \mathfrak{B}(G, M, I) \\ A &\mapsto (A, A'). \end{aligned}$$

This function is well-defined because A is the extent of some concept, therefore $(A, A') = (A'', A')$ is a concept. The function φ is surjective because every concept (A, B) can also be written as (A, A') . The function is obviously injective, therefore φ is a bijection. Furthermore, φ is an isomorphism because, by definition, it holds that

$$A_1 \subseteq A_2 \Leftrightarrow (A_1, A'_1) \leq (A_2, A'_2).$$

Dually, we define

$$\begin{aligned} \psi: \mathfrak{I}(G, M, I) &\rightarrow \mathfrak{B}(G, M, I) \\ B &\mapsto (B', B). \end{aligned}$$

It follows analogously that ψ is a well-defined bijection. The function ψ is monotone because of Lemma 3.9. Hence, ψ is an isomorphism. $\square$

Due to this proposition, we know that the concept lattice of a formal context is completely determined by the affiliated intents and extents.

3.3 Standard context

Theorem 3.12 ([4, Theorem 3]). *A complete lattice L is isomorphic to the concept lattice $\mathfrak{B}(G, M, I)$ if and only if there exist maps $\gamma: G \rightarrow L$ and $\mu: M \rightarrow L$ which satisfy the following conditions:*

3 FORMAL CONCEPT ANALYSIS

- (i) $\gamma[G]$ is supremum-dense in L .
- (ii) $\mu[M]$ is infimum-dense in L .
- (iii) $\forall m \in M \forall g \in G: g I m \Leftrightarrow \gamma(g) \leq \mu(m)$.

In particular, it holds that a complete lattice $(L, \leq)$ is isomorphic to the concept lattice of $\mathfrak{B}(L, L, \leq)$.

Proof. For a proof of this theorem, we refer to [4, pp. 20–22]. □

Definition 3.13. Let (G, M, I) be a formal context. For an object $g \in G$, we define its corresponding *object concept*

$$\gamma g := (g'', g').$$

Symmetrically, the *attribute concept* for an attribute $m \in M$ is given by

$$\mu m := (m', m'').$$

Definition 3.14. A formal context (G, M, I) is called *clarified* if $g' = h'$ implies $g = h$ for every $g, h \in G$ and $m' = n'$ implies $m = n$ for every $n, m \in M$.

Definition 3.15. An object $g \in G$ is called *reducible* if there exists a set $X \subseteq G \setminus \{g\}$ such that $g' = X'$. Dually, an attribute $m \in M$ is called *reducible* if there exists a set $Y \subseteq M \setminus \{m\}$ such that $m' = Y'$.

Remark 3.16. Distinct objects $g, h \in G$ with identical intents $g' = h'$ are reducible. Furthermore, objects which satisfy $g' = M$ are always reducible because $g' = M = \emptyset'$. Symmetric results hold for attributes.

Lemma 3.17. For arbitrary sets $X \subseteq G$ and $Y \subseteq M$, it holds that

$$(X'', X') = \bigvee_{x \in X} (x'', x') \text{ and } (Y', Y'') = \bigwedge_{y \in Y} (y', y'').$$

In particular, we get that the set of object concepts $\gamma[G]$ is supremum-dense and the set of attribute concepts $\mu[M]$ is infimum-dense in $\mathfrak{B}(G, M, I)$.

Proof. Let $X \subseteq G$ be an arbitrary set of objects. By Lemma 3.5, we obtain that

$$X' = \left(\bigcup_{x \in X} \{x\} \right)' = \bigcap_{x \in X} \{x\}',$$

and this is the intent of $\bigvee_{x \in X} (x'', x')$ according to Theorem 3.10. Hence, we have that

$$(X'', X') = \bigvee_{x \in X} (x'', x').$$

3 FORMAL CONCEPT ANALYSIS

as concepts are uniquely determined by their intents. Additionally, we obtain that the set of all object concepts $\gamma[G]$ is supremum-dense in $\mathfrak{B}(G, M, I)$ because for an arbitrary concept (A, B) , it holds that

$$(A, B) = (A'', A') = \bigvee_{x \in A} (x'', x') = \bigvee_{x \in A} \gamma x.$$

These results can be proven symmetrically for attributes. □

Lemma 3.18. *Let (G, M, I) be a clarified context. An object is reducible if and only if the corresponding object concept is supremum-reducible in the concept lattice $\mathfrak{B}(G, M, I)$. Dually, an attribute is reducible if and only if the corresponding attribute concept is infimum-reducible in the concept lattice $\mathfrak{B}(G, M, I)$.*

Proof. “ $\Rightarrow$ ”: Let $g \in G$ and $X \subseteq G \setminus \{g\}$ such that $X' = g'$. By Lemma 3.17, it holds that

$$(g'', g') = (X'', X') = \bigvee_{x \in X} (x'', x').$$

Therefore, we have that $(x'', x') \leq (g'', g')$ for every $x \in X$. The context is clarified and $g \neq x$, hence we know that $(x'', x') < (g'', g')$ for $x \in X$. We thus have shown that the object concept γg is supremum-reducible.

“ $\Leftarrow$ ”: Let $g \in G$ such that γg is supremum-reducible, i.e.,

$$\gamma g = \bigvee \{C \in \mathfrak{B}(G, M, I) \mid C < \gamma g\}.$$

We define the set $X := \{x \in G \mid \gamma x < \gamma g\}$. Using the fact that the set of all object concepts is supremum-dense in $\mathfrak{B}(G, M, I)$, we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma g &= \bigvee_{C < \gamma g} C \\ &= \bigvee_{C < \gamma g} \bigvee \{\gamma x \mid x \in G, \gamma x \leq C\} \\ &\leq \bigvee \{\gamma x \mid x \in G, \gamma x < \gamma g\} \\ &= \bigvee_{x \in X} \gamma x \\ &\leq \gamma g. \end{aligned}$$

As shown above, we get that

$$(g'', g') = \gamma g = \bigvee_{x \in X} \gamma x = \bigvee_{x \in X} (x'', x') = (X'', X').$$

Hence, we have shown that $g' = X'$, and $g \notin X$.

This result can be proven symmetrically for attributes. □

3 FORMAL CONCEPT ANALYSIS

Lemma 3.19. *Let $g \in G$ and $m \in M$ be reducible. It holds that the following lattices are isomorphic:*

$$\mathfrak{B}(G, M, I) \cong \mathfrak{B}(G \setminus \{g\}, M, I) \cong \mathfrak{B}(G, M \setminus \{m\}, I).$$

Proof. Because of Lemma 3.17, we know that $\gamma[G]$ is supremum-dense in $\mathfrak{B}(G, M, I)$. The set $\gamma[G \setminus \{g\}]$ is also supremum-dense in $\mathfrak{B}(G, M, I)$ because the concept γg is supremum-reducible by Lemma 3.18. Hence, we get

$$\mathfrak{B}(G, M, I) \cong \mathfrak{B}(G \setminus \{g\}, M, I)$$

by Theorem 3.12. Symmetrically, it can be shown that

$$\mathfrak{B}(G, M, I) \cong \mathfrak{B}(G, M \setminus \{m\}, I). \quad \square$$

Removing a reducible object or attribute is called *reducing* the context.

Definition 3.20. A clarified context is called *row reduced* if every object is irreducible and *column reduced* if every attribute is irreducible. A clarified context is called *reduced* if it is row reduced and column reduced.

Recall that $J(L)$ denotes the set of all supremum-irreducible elements and $M(L)$ denotes the set of all infimum-irreducible elements of a complete lattice L .

Proposition 3.21 ([3, Proposition 3]). *For every finite lattice L , there exists a reduced context $\mathbb{K}(L)$ such that $L \cong \mathfrak{B}(\mathbb{K}(L))$, which is given by*

$$\mathbb{K}(L) := (J(L), M(L), \leq).$$

The formal context $\mathbb{K}(L)$ is called the *standard context* of L .

Proof. In Lemma 2.8, we have shown that $J(L)$ is supremum-dense in L and $M(L)$ is infimum-dense in L . By using Theorem 3.12, we immediately obtain that

$$\mathfrak{B}(J(L), M(L), \leq) \cong L.$$

We still need to prove that $\mathbb{K}(L)$ is a reduced context. Assume that there exists a reducible object $g \in J(L)$, i.e., there exists a set of objects $X \subseteq J(L) \setminus \{g\}$ such that $X' = g$. We will show that g is supremum-reducible, i.e., $g = \bigvee \{h \in L \mid h < g\}$. We have that

$$\begin{aligned} X' &= \{m \in M(L) \mid \forall x \in X: x \leq m\} \\ &= \{m \in M(L) \mid \bigvee X \leq m\}. \end{aligned}$$

4 CENTRALIZING MONOIDS ON FINITE SETS

Furthermore, for every $y \in L$ we have $y = \bigwedge \{m \in M(L) \mid y \leq m\}$ since $M(L)$ is infimum-dense in L . Therefore, it holds that

$$\begin{aligned} \{m \in M(L) \mid y \leq m\}' &= \{h \in J(L) \mid \forall m \in M(L): m \geq y \Rightarrow h \leq m\} \\ &= \{h \in J(L) \mid h \leq y\}. \end{aligned}$$

Using $y = g$, we obtain $g'' = \{h \in J(L) \mid h \leq g\}$. Additionally, we get that

$$X'' = \{m \in M(L) \mid \bigvee X \leq m\}' = \{h \in J(L) \mid h \leq \bigvee X\}$$

by using $y = \bigvee X$. We know that $A \mapsto A''$ is a closure operator by Corollary 3.4 and hence we obtain that

$$X \subseteq X'' = g'' = \{h \in J(L) \mid h \leq g\}.$$

Therefore, we know that $x \leq g$ for every $x \in X$. Hence, it holds that $\bigvee X \leq g$. Furthermore, $g \notin X$ implies $x < g$ for every $x \in X$. Conversely, we know that

$$\{h \in J(L) \mid h \leq g\} = g'' = X'' = \{h \in J(L) \mid h \leq \bigvee X\}.$$

We obtain that $g \leq \bigvee X$ because $g \in g''$. We have shown that g is supremum-reducible, which is a contradiction to $g \in J(L)$. Symmetrically, it can be shown that every attribute $m \in M(L)$ is irreducible. $\square$

4 Centralizing monoids on finite sets

4.1 Commutation and centralizers

Definition 4.1. For a nonempty set A and a positive integer $n \in \mathbb{N}_+$, denote the set of all maps from A^n into A by $\mathcal{O}_A^{(n)}$. Furthermore, we define

$$\mathcal{O}_A := \bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} \mathcal{O}_A^{(n)}.$$

A function $f \in \mathcal{O}_A$ is often called an operation on the set A . Unless stated otherwise, we consider A to be a finite set throughout this thesis.

Definition 4.2. Let n, m be positive integers, $f \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(n)}$ and $g \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(m)}$. We say that f *commutes* with g if for every matrix $M \in A^{m \times n}$ with rows $(r_i)_{i=1}^m$ and columns $(c_j)_{j=1}^n$, the following equation holds:

$$f(g(c_1), \dots, g(c_n)) = g(f(r_1), \dots, f(r_m)).$$

We will use the abbreviation $\perp$ to denote this relation:

$$f \perp g :\Leftrightarrow f \text{ commutes with } g.$$

4 CENTRALIZING MONOIDS ON FINITE SETS

By looking at the definition of this relation, it becomes apparent that it is a symmetric relation, i.e., $f \perp g \Leftrightarrow g \perp f$. For $n = m = 1$, this definition coincides with the commutativity of composition for unary functions:

$$f(g(x)) = g(f(x)) \text{ for all } x \in A (= A^{1 \times 1}).$$

Therefore, this definition for multi-variable functions can be viewed as an extension of the commutativity for single-variable functions.

Definition 4.3. For a set of functions $F \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$, the *centralizer* F^* is defined by

$$F^* := \{g \in \mathcal{O}_A \mid \forall f \in F: f \perp g\}.$$

We usually write f^* instead of $\{f\}^*$ and F^{**} instead of $(F^*)^*$. Furthermore, we define the n -ary part of the centralizer:

$$F^{*(n)} := F^* \cap \mathcal{O}_A^{(n)} = \{g \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(n)} \mid \forall f \in F: f \perp g\}.$$

Similarly, we usually use $f^{*(n)}$ as an abbreviation for $\{f\}^{*(n)}$. In particular, the unary centralizer

$$F^{*(1)} = F^* \cap \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)} = \{g \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)} \mid \forall f \in F: f \perp g\}$$

will play a crucial role throughout this thesis. We usually write $F^{**(1)}$ instead of $(F^*)^{*(1)}$ and $F^{*(1)*}$ instead of $(F^{*(1)})^*$.

4.2 Formal context of commutation

In this subsection, we will introduce the *formal context of commutation* $\mathbb{K}_c := (\mathcal{O}_A, \mathcal{O}_A, \perp)$. Unsurprisingly, there is a direct connection between the context of commutation and the centralization operator $F \mapsto F^*$. For a subset $F \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$, we have that

$$F' = \{g \in \mathcal{O}_A \mid \forall f \in F: f \perp g\} = F^*.$$

Therefore, the derivation operator $F \mapsto F'$ of the context $\mathbb{K}_c$ and the centralization operator $F \mapsto F^*$ on $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{O}_A)$ coincide. Note that the derivation operators on the set of objects and the set of attributes are identical in the context $\mathbb{K}_c$ because the relation $\perp$ is symmetric and $M = G = \mathcal{O}_A$. Hence, we can use the results of Section 3 to obtain properties of the centralization operator:

Proposition 4.4. *The map $F \mapsto F^*$ induces a Galois connection between $\mathcal{O}_A$ and $\mathcal{O}_A$, i.e., $F \mapsto F^*$ fulfills the following conditions for any $F, G \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$:*

- (i) $F \subseteq G \Rightarrow F^* \supseteq G^*$.
- (ii) $F \subseteq F^{**}$.

4 CENTRALIZING MONOIDS ON FINITE SETS

Proof. Corollary 3.4 in the formal context $\mathbb{K}_c := (\mathcal{O}_A, \mathcal{O}_A, \perp)$ provides the desired result. $\square$

Corollary 4.5. *The following facts hold:*

- (i) $F^{***} = F^*$ for $F \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$.
- (ii) The map $F \mapsto F^{**}$ is a closure operator on $\mathcal{O}_A$.

Proof. This follows immediately from Lemma 2.6 and Proposition 2.7. $\square$

In particular, the subcontext $\mathbb{K}_1 := (\mathcal{O}_A, \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}, \perp \cap (\mathcal{O}_A \times \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}))$, which we will simply denote by $(\mathcal{O}_A, \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}, \perp)$ and call the *formal context of unary centralizers*, will play an essential role throughout this thesis. Once again, the derivation operators coincide with centralization operators. For $F \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$ and $G \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$, we get the following:

$$\begin{aligned} F^\uparrow &= \{s \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)} \mid \forall f \in F: f \perp s\} = F^{*(1)}. \\ G^\downarrow &= \{h \in \mathcal{O}_A \mid \forall g \in G: h \perp g\} = G^*. \end{aligned}$$

Once again, we can use the results of Section 3:

Proposition 4.6. *The pair $F \mapsto F^*$ and $G \mapsto G^{*(1)}$ is a Galois connection between $\mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$ and $\mathcal{O}_A$, i.e., the following conditions are fulfilled:*

- (i) $F_1 \subseteq F_2 \Rightarrow F_1^* \supseteq F_2^*$ for $F_1, F_2 \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$.
- (ii) $G_1 \subseteq G_2 \Rightarrow G_1^{*(1)} \supseteq G_2^{*(1)}$ for $G_1, G_2 \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$.
- (iii) $F \subseteq F^{**^{(1)}}$ and $G \subseteq G^{*(1)*}$ for $F \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}, G \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$.

Proof. This follows immediately by Corollary 3.4 in the formal context $\mathbb{K}_1 = (\mathcal{O}_A, \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}, \perp)$. $\square$

Corollary 4.7. *For any sets $F \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$ and $G \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$, the following facts hold:*

- (i) $((F^*)^{*(1)})^* = F^*$ and $((G^{*(1)})^*)^{*(1)} = G^{*(1)}$.
- (ii) The maps $F \mapsto F^{**^{(1)}}$ and $G \mapsto G^{*(1)*}$ are closure operators on $\mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$ and $\mathcal{O}_A$, respectively.
- (iii) $G \subseteq F^* \Leftrightarrow F \subseteq G^{*(1)}$.

Proof. By Lemma 2.6 and Proposition 2.7, we obtain that $F \mapsto F^*$ and $G \mapsto G^{*(1)}$ have the desired properties because the pair $F \mapsto F^*$ and $G \mapsto G^{*(1)}$ is a Galois connection between $\mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$ and $\mathcal{O}_A$. Note that (iii) follows from Proposition 3.3 (iv) applied to the context $(\mathcal{O}_A, \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}, \perp)$. $\square$

Lemma 4.8. *Let $F_i \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$ for $i \in I$. Then the following equations hold:*

$$\left(\bigcup_{i \in I} F_i \right)^* = \bigcap_{i \in I} F_i^* \quad \text{and} \quad \left(\bigcup_{i \in I} F_i \right)^{*(1)} = \bigcap_{i \in I} F_i^{*(1)}.$$

In particular, we get that

$$F^* = \bigcap_{f \in F} f^* \quad \text{and} \quad F^{*(1)} = \bigcap_{f \in F} f^{*(1)}$$

for every $F \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$.

Proof. Both equations follow immediately by Lemma 3.5 applied to the formal contexts $(\mathcal{O}_A, \mathcal{O}_A, \perp)$ and $(\mathcal{O}_A, \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}, \perp)$. $\square$

4.3 Centralizing monoids

Definition 4.9. A subset $M \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$ is called a *transformation monoid* if it contains the identity and is closed under composition.

Definition 4.10. A subset $M \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$ is called a *centralizing monoid* if

$$M = M^{**^{(1)}}.$$

Remark 4.11. Every centralizing monoid M is also a transformation monoid. The identity $\text{id}: A \rightarrow A$ commutes with every $f \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(n)}$ for any $n \in \mathbb{N}_+$, hence $\text{id} \in M^{**^{(1)}} = M$. A function $f \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$ is contained in the set $M = M^{**^{(1)}}$ if and only if it commutes with every function $h \in M^* \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$. Let $f, g \in M$ and $h \in M^*$ be an n -ary function for $n \in \mathbb{N}_+$. It obviously holds that $f \circ g \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$. Furthermore, we need to show that $f \circ g$ commutes with h . For an arbitrary tuple $(x_1, \dots, x_n) \in A^n$, we obtain the desired equation by using $f \perp h$ and $g \perp h$:

$$\begin{aligned} (f \circ g)(h(x_1, \dots, x_n)) &= f(g(h(x_1, \dots, x_n))) \\ &= f(h(g(x_1), \dots, g(x_n))) \\ &= h(f(g(x_1)), \dots, f(g(x_n))) \\ &= h(f \circ g(x_1), \dots, f \circ g(x_n)). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, we have that $f \circ g \in M^{**^{(1)}} = M$.

Theorem 4.12 ([7, Lemma 2.2]). *The following statements are equivalent:*

- (i) M is a centralizing monoid.
- (ii) There exists $F \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$ such that $M = F^{*(1)}$.
- (iii) There exists an algebra $\mathcal{A} = (A; F)$ such that $M = \text{End}(\mathcal{A})$.

Proof. “(i) $\Rightarrow$ (ii)”: Trivial with $F = M^*$.

“(i) $\Leftarrow$ (ii)”: Let $F \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$ such that $M = F^{*(1)}$. Because of Corollary 4.7, we know that $(F^{*(1)})^{**(1)} = F^{*(1)}$ and we thus immediately obtain that

$$M^{**(1)} = (F^{*(1)})^{**(1)} = F^{*(1)} = M.$$

“(ii) $\Leftrightarrow$ (iii)”: Let $F \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$. A function $\varphi \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$ is an endomorphism of $\mathcal{A} = (A; F)$ if and only if

$$f(\varphi(x_1), \dots, \varphi(x_n)) = \varphi(f(x_1, \dots, x_n)) \text{ for every } f \in F.$$

Therefore, a function $\varphi \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$ is an endomorphism of $\mathcal{A}$ if and only if $\varphi \in F^*$. Hence, we have

$$\text{End}(\mathcal{A}) = F^* \cap \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)} = F^{*(1)}. \quad \square$$

Due to this theorem, we know that the set of all centralizing monoids can be expressed as $\{F^{*(1)} \mid F \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A\}$. Furthermore, this theorem ensures that set of all centralizing monoids equals the set of all endomorphism monoids of algebras on the set A .

4.4 Witnesses for centralizing monoids

Definition 4.13. A subset $S \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$ is called a *witness* for a centralizing monoid M if it fulfills $M = S^{*(1)}$.

For any centralizing monoid M , the set M^* is obviously a witness for M . Hence, every centralizing monoid has a witness. In fact, M^* is the largest witness for M since any witness $S \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$ satisfies $M = S^{*(1)}$ and hence $M^* = S^{*(1)*} \supseteq S$ by Proposition 4.6 (iii).

Proposition 4.14 ([6, Theorem 2.5]). *Every centralizing monoid M on a finite set A has a finite witness.*

Proof. Let A be a finite set and $M \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$ be a centralizing monoid. Let $S \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$ be a witness for M (for example $S = M^*$). We know that for every $h \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)} \setminus M$ there exists $f_h \in S$ which does not commute with h because $\forall f \in S: f \perp h$ would imply $h \in S^{*(1)} = M$. Now we define

$$\tilde{S} := \{f_h \in S \mid h \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)} \setminus M\}.$$

4 CENTRALIZING MONOIDS ON FINITE SETS

The set $\mathcal{O}_A^{(1)} = A^A$ is finite because A is finite. Therefore, $\tilde{S}$ is also finite. Let $h \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)} \setminus M$. The set $\tilde{S}$ contains a function f_h which fulfills $h \not\perp f_h$. Hence, it holds that

$$h \notin \tilde{S}^{*(1)} = \{g \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)} \mid \forall f \in \tilde{S}: f \perp g\}.$$

Consequently, we have proven that $\tilde{S}^{*(1)} \subseteq M$, and the inclusion $\tilde{S} \subseteq S$ implies $\tilde{S}^{*(1)} \supseteq S^{*(1)} = M$. We thus know that $\tilde{S}$ is a witness for M . $\square$

Remark 4.15. This proof provides a simple theoretical algorithm to find a finite witness S for a centralizing monoid M .

For all $h \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)} \setminus M$:

- (1) find $g \in M^*$ such that $g \not\perp h$
- (2) add g to S

Although A is a finite set, $\mathcal{O}_A$ is countably infinite. Therefore, finding a suitable function g in step (1) might computationally be very expensive. Hence, it is desirable to find a small finite subset of $\mathcal{O}_A$ which contains a suitable g for every centralizing monoid M and every $h \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)} \setminus M$. The following lemmata will provide precisely that.

Definition 4.16. Let $n, k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $1 \leq k < n$. A function

$$\beta: \{1, \dots, n\} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, k\}$$

induces a variable identification of n -ary operations as follows. For $f \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(n)}$, the k -ary function

$$\delta_\beta f(x_1, \dots, x_k) := f(x_{\beta(1)}, \dots, x_{\beta(n)})$$

is called a variable identification of f . We say that a set $F \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$ is closed under variable identifications if $\delta_\beta f \in F$ for every n -ary $f \in F$ and every variable identification map β as above.

Although it is technically not the same, we will sometimes denote variable identification maps by $\beta: n \rightarrow k$ instead of $\beta: \{1, \dots, n\} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, k\}$ to make certain statements more readable.

Lemma 4.17. Let $f \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(n)}$ and $\beta: \{1, \dots, n\} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, k\}$ be an n -ary variable identification map. If f commutes with a function $g \in \mathcal{O}_A$, then $\delta_\beta f$ also commutes with g , i.e.,

$$\forall g \in \mathcal{O}_A: f \perp g \Rightarrow \delta_\beta f \perp g.$$

4 CENTRALIZING MONOIDS ON FINITE SETS

Proof. Let $g \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(m)}$ such that $f \perp g$ and $B \in A^{m \times k}$ with rows $(r_i)_{i=1}^m$ and columns $(c_j)_{j=1}^k$, i.e., $r_i = (b_{ij})_{j=1}^k$ and $c_j = (b_{ij})_{i=1}^m$. Define the matrix $B' \in A^{m \times n}$ such that $b'_{ij} := b_{i\beta(j)}$ for $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ and $j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. The rows of the matrix B' can be represented as $r'_i = (b_{i\beta(j)})_{j=1}^n$ and the columns as $c'_j = (b_{i\beta(j)})_{i=1}^m$. We know that f and g commute, hence the following equation holds:

$$f(g(c'_1), \dots, g(c'_n)) = g(f(r'_1), \dots, f(r'_m)).$$

Using this equation, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_\beta f(g(c_1), \dots, g(c_k)) &= f(g(c_{\beta(1)}), \dots, g(c_{\beta(n)})) \\ &= f(g(b_{1\beta(1)}, \dots, b_{m\beta(1)}), \dots, g(b_{1\beta(n)}, \dots, b_{m\beta(n)})) \\ &= f(g(c'_1), \dots, g(c'_n)) \\ &= g(f(r'_1), \dots, f(r'_m)) \\ &= g(f(b_{1\beta(1)}, \dots, b_{1\beta(n)}), \dots, f(b_{m\beta(1)}, \dots, b_{m\beta(n)})) \\ &= g(\delta_\beta f(b_{11}, \dots, b_{1k}), \dots, \delta_\beta f(b_{m1}, \dots, b_{mk})) \\ &= g(\delta_\beta f(r_1), \dots, \delta_\beta f(r_m)). \end{aligned} \quad \square$$

Corollary 4.18. *For every $F \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$, the centralizer F^* is closed under variable identifications.*

Proof. Let $f \in F^*$ be an n -ary function and $\beta: \{1, \dots, n\} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, k\}$ such that $k < n$. We will show that $\forall g \in F: \delta_\beta f \perp g$. To this end, let $g \in F$. We know that $f \perp g$ because $g \in F$ and $f \in F^*$. Using Lemma 4.17, it follows that $\delta_\beta f \perp g$. Hence, we have that $\delta_\beta f \in F^*$. $\square$

Lemma 4.19. *Let A be a set with $|A| = k$ for $k > 1$. Consider $s \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$ and $f \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(n)}$ with $n > k$ such that $f \not\perp s$. Then there exists a variable identification $\delta_\beta f \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(k)}$ such that $\delta_\beta f \not\perp s$ and*

$$\forall s' \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}: f \perp s' \Rightarrow \delta_\beta f \perp s'.$$

Proof. Let $A = \{a_1, \dots, a_k\}$, $s: A \rightarrow A$ and $f: A^n \rightarrow A$ with $n > k$ and $f \not\perp s$. By definition, it holds that

$$f \not\perp s \Leftrightarrow \exists c_1, \dots, c_n \in A: s(f(c_1, \dots, c_n)) \neq f(s(c_1), \dots, s(c_n)).$$

Let $\beta: \{1, \dots, n\} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, k\}$ be the function which satisfies $c_i = a_{\beta(i)}$ for every $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. With the help of the variable identification map β , we obtain the function $\delta_\beta f: A^k \rightarrow A$:

$$\delta_\beta f(x_1, \dots, x_k) := f(x_{\beta(1)}, \dots, x_{\beta(n)}).$$

4 CENTRALIZING MONOIDS ON FINITE SETS

Consequently, we get the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned}
 s(\delta_\beta f(a_1, \dots, a_k)) &= s(f(a_{\beta(1)}, \dots, a_{\beta(n)})) \\
 &= s(f(c_1, \dots, c_n)) \\
 &\neq f(s(c_1), \dots, s(c_n)) \\
 &= f(s(a_{\beta(1)}), \dots, s(a_{\beta(n)})) \\
 &= \delta_\beta f(s(a_1), \dots, s(a_k)).
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$s(\delta_\beta f(a_1, \dots, a_k)) \neq \delta_\beta f(s(a_1), \dots, s(a_k)),$$

which proves that $\delta_\beta f \not\perp s$. Furthermore, we know that

$$\forall s' \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)} : f \perp s' \Rightarrow \delta_\beta f \perp s'$$

by Lemma 4.17. □

For $|A| = k$, Lemma 4.19 ensures that replacing $\mathcal{O}_A$ with $\bigcup_{i=1}^k \mathcal{O}_A^{(i)}$ in step 2 of the algorithm presented in Remark 4.15 is feasible.

Corollary 4.20. *Let $|A| = k$. For every centralizing monoid $M \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$, there exists a finite witness $S \subseteq \bigcup_{i=1}^k \mathcal{O}_A^{(i)}$.*

Proof. We can adapt the proof of Proposition 4.14 by using Lemma 4.19. Let $M \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$ be a centralizing monoid. We know that for every $s \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)} \setminus M$ there exists $f_s \in M^*$ which does not commute with s , i.e., $s \not\perp f_s$. If the arity of f_s is bigger than k , then Lemma 4.19 yields a function $g_s \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(k)}$ with the same properties. Otherwise, we simply set $g_s := f_s$. Now we define

$$S = \{g_s \mid s \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)} \setminus M\} \subseteq \bigcup_{i=1}^k \mathcal{O}_A^{(i)}.$$

Analogously to the proof of Proposition 4.14, it follows that S is a finite witness for M . □

Lemma 4.21. *Let $s \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$, $f \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(n)}$ such that $n \geq 2$, and $a_1, \dots, a_n \in A$ such that $a_i = a_j$ for some $1 \leq i < j \leq n$ which fulfill*

$$s(f(a_1, \dots, a_n)) \neq f(s(a_1), \dots, s(a_n)).$$

Then the $(n-1)$ -ary function

$$\Delta_{ij} f(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}) := f(x_1, \dots, x_{j-1}, x_i, x_j, \dots, x_{n-1})$$

does not commute with s .

4 CENTRALIZING MONOIDS ON FINITE SETS

Note that $\Delta_{ij}f$ is a variable identification of f . The corresponding variable identification map $\beta: \{1, \dots, n\} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, n-1\}$ is given for $1 \leq k \leq n$ as:

$$\beta(k) = \begin{cases} k & \text{if } 1 \leq k < j, \\ i & \text{if } k = j, \\ k-1 & \text{if } j < k \leq n. \end{cases}$$

Proof. Define the tuple $(b_1, \dots, b_{n-1})$ for $1 \leq k \leq n-1$ by

$$b_k := \begin{cases} a_k & \text{if } k < j, \\ a_{k+1} & \text{if } k \geq j. \end{cases}$$

From $(b_1, \dots, b_{n-1}) = (a_1, \dots, a_{j-1}, a_{j+1}, \dots, a_n)$ and $a_i = a_j$, we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} s(\Delta_{ij}f(b_1, \dots, b_{n-1})) &= s(f(b_1, \dots, b_{j-1}, b_i, b_j, \dots, b_{n-1})) \\ &= s(f(a_1, \dots, a_{j-1}, a_i, a_{j+1}, \dots, a_n)) \\ &= s(f(a_1, \dots, a_n)) \\ &\neq f(s(a_1), \dots, s(a_n)) \\ &= f(s(a_1), \dots, s(a_{j-1}), s(a_i), s(a_{j+1}), \dots, s(a_n)) \\ &= f(s(b_1), \dots, s(b_{j-1}), s(b_i), s(b_j), \dots, s(b_{n-1})) \\ &= \Delta_{ij}f(s(b_1), \dots, s(b_{n-1})). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, we have shown that $\Delta_{ij}f \not\prec s$. □

Proposition 4.22. *Let $s \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$, $F \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$ be closed under variable identifications and $f \in F \setminus s^*$ be of minimal arity n . Then the following facts hold:*

- (i) *Every variable identification of f belongs to s^* .*
- (ii) $n \leq |A|$.
- (iii) $\forall a \in A^n$: *a non-injective* $\Rightarrow s(f(a)) = f(s \circ a)$.
- (iv) $\exists a \in A^n$ *injective*: $s(f(a)) \neq f(s \circ a)$.

Note that for a tuple $a = (a_1, \dots, a_n) \in A^n$, we have that

$$(s \circ a)(i) = s(a(i)) = s(a_i) \text{ for } i \in \{1, \dots, n\}.$$

Therefore, $s \circ a$ corresponds to the tuple $(s(a_1), \dots, s(a_n))$.

Proof. (i) Let $k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $1 \leq k < n$ and $\beta: \{1, \dots, n\} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, k\}$. We know that $\delta_\beta f \in F$ because F is closed under variable identifications. Additionally, f has minimal arity n in $F \setminus s^*$ and $\delta_\beta f$ has arity $k < n$. Thus it follows that $\delta_\beta f \notin F \setminus s^*$. We obtain $\delta_\beta f \in s^*$ because $\delta_\beta f \in F$ and $\delta_\beta f \notin F \setminus s^*$.

- (iii) Let $a = (a_1, \dots, a_n) \in A^n$ be non-injective, i.e., $a_i = a_j$ for some $1 \leq i < j \leq n$. Assume $s(f(a_1, \dots, a_n)) \neq f(s(a_1), \dots, s(a_n))$. Because of Lemma 4.21, we know that there exists the $(n - 1)$ -ary variable identification $\Delta_{ij}f$ which does not commute with s . Furthermore, $\Delta_{ij}f \in F \setminus s^*$ because F is closed under variable identifications. This contradicts the minimality of the arity of f in $F \setminus s^*$.
- (ii) If $n > |A|$, then every n -tuple is non-injective and thus (iii) implies that f commutes with s , which is a contradiction. Hence, it holds that $n \leq |A|$.
- (iv) From the contraposition of (iii), we obtain the following:

$$\forall a \in A^n : s(f(a)) \neq f(s \circ a) \Rightarrow a \text{ injective.}$$

We know that $f \notin s^*$, which is equivalent to

$$\exists a \in A^n : s(f(a)) \neq f(s \circ a).$$

Such $a \in A^n$ has to be injective. □

5 Witness-complete sets

In this section, we will take a closer look at the formal context of unary centralizers $\mathbb{K}_1 = (\mathcal{O}_A, \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}, \perp)$. For $F \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$ and $G \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$, we recall the derivation operators on $\mathbb{K}_1$:

$$\begin{aligned} F^\uparrow &= \{s \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)} \mid \forall f \in F : f \perp s\} = F^{*(1)}. \\ G^\downarrow &= \{h \in \mathcal{O}_A \mid \forall g \in G : h \perp g\} = G^*. \end{aligned}$$

By definition, a set $M \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$ is a centralizing monoid if $M = M^{** (1)}$. In Proposition 3.7, we have shown that a set $M \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$ is the intent of some concept of the context $\mathbb{K}_1$ if and only if $M = M''$. In this formal context, we know that $M'' = M^{** (1)}$. Hence, it holds that $M \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$ is a centralizing monoid if and only if it is the intent of some concept in $\mathbb{K}_1$. If we are able to determine the concept lattice of the context $\mathbb{K}_1$, then we also obtain every centralizing monoid by simply taking the intent of every concept in $\mathfrak{B}(\mathcal{O}_A, \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}, \perp)$. In this thesis, this approach will be used to identify every centralizing monoid on a set with three elements.

Definition 5.1. A set of operations $W \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$ is called witness-complete if every centralizing monoid has a witness which is a subset of W .

The set $\mathcal{O}_A$ is countably infinite, which means that we need to reduce the size of the context $\mathbb{K}_1$ to compute the concept lattice, i.e., we need to find

5 WITNESS-COMPLETE SETS

a finite and preferably small subcontext of $\mathbb{K}_1$ which has an isomorphic concept lattice. In Corollary 4.20, we have proven that the finite set

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^k \mathcal{O}_A^{(n)} \text{ for } k = |A|$$

is witness-complete. The following proposition will clarify how we can use a finite witness-complete set of operations to find a suitable finite subcontext of $\mathbb{K}_1$:

Proposition 5.2. *Let $W \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$ be a witness-complete set of operations. Then the concept lattices $\mathfrak{B}(\mathcal{O}_A, \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}, \perp)$ and $\mathfrak{B}(W, \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}, \perp)$ are isomorphic. Furthermore, the intents of the concepts of these contexts are identical, i.e.,*

$$\mathfrak{I}(\mathcal{O}_A, \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}, \perp) = \mathfrak{I}(W, \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}, \perp).$$

Proof. Because of Proposition 3.11, it suffices to show that the sets of intents of the two contexts are identical. Note that for a formal context (G, M, I) , we can express the set of all intents as $\{A' : A \subseteq G\}$. From this expression and $W \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$, we immediately obtain that

$$\mathfrak{I}(W, \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}, \perp) = \{F^{*(1)} : F \subseteq W\} \subseteq \{F^{*(1)} : F \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A\} = \mathfrak{I}(\mathcal{O}_A, \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}, \perp).$$

Let $M \in \mathfrak{I}(\mathcal{O}_A, \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}, \perp)$, i.e., M is the intent of some concept in $\mathbb{K}_1$. From Proposition 3.7, we get $M = M'' = M^{**^{(1)}}$, which means that M is a centralizing monoid. Let $S \subseteq W$ be a witness for M . Now we have

$$M = S^{*(1)} \in \{F^{*(1)} : F \subseteq W\} = \mathfrak{I}(W, \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}, \perp). \quad \square$$

This proposition ensures that it suffices to compute the concept lattice of $(W, \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}, \perp)$ for a witness-complete set W to identify every centralizing monoid.

For a set $F \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$, we will use the following abbreviation to denote the subset of F containing every function of arity $k \leq n$:

$$F^{\leq n} := F \cap \bigcup_{k=1}^n \mathcal{O}_A^{(k)}.$$

Lemma 5.3. *For every $s \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$ there exists an $n_s \in \mathbb{N}_+$ such that for every $F \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$, which is closed under variable identifications, the following implication holds:*

$$F \not\subseteq s^* \Rightarrow F^{\leq n_s} \not\subseteq s^*.$$

This implication is equivalent to the following statement:

$$F \setminus s^* \neq \emptyset \Rightarrow \exists f \in F \setminus s^* : f \text{ has arity } k \leq n_s.$$

5 WITNESS-COMplete SETS

Proof. We can simply choose $n_s = |A|$. Let $f \in F \setminus s^* \neq \emptyset$ be of minimal arity. It follows that $n \leq |A| = n_s$ by Proposition 4.22 (ii). Hence, we know that $f \in F^{\leq n_s}$ and therefore also $f \in F^{\leq n_s} \setminus s^*$. $\square$

Remark 5.4. The proof of Lemma 5.3 ensures that $n_s = |A|$ is a valid choice for every $s \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$. In general, $|A|$ is not the minimal positive integer which fulfills the condition in Lemma 5.3. For example, consider the constant function c_a for $a \in A$, i.e., the function which is defined as $c_a(x) := a$ for every $x \in A$. Let $f \in F \setminus c_a^*$ be an n -ary function and let $(x_1, \dots, x_n) \in A^n$ such that

$$c_a(f(x_1, \dots, x_n)) \neq f(c_a(x_1), \dots, c_a(x_n)).$$

We obtain the following equations using $c_a(x) = a$ for every $x \in A$:

$$\begin{aligned} c_a(f(x_1, \dots, x_n)) &= a \\ f(c_a(x_1), \dots, c_a(x_n)) &= f(a, \dots, a). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, we know that $a \neq f(a, \dots, a)$. Define the trivial variable identification map $\beta(i) := 1$ for $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. For any $x \in A$, the function $\delta_\beta f \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$ fulfills

$$c_a(\delta_\beta f(x)) = a \neq f(a, \dots, a) = \delta_\beta f(a) = \delta_\beta f(c_a(x)),$$

and we thus get $\delta_\beta f \notin c_a^*$. We know that $\delta_\beta f \in F$ because the set F in Lemma 5.3 is closed under variable identifications, and hence $\delta_\beta f \in F \setminus c_a^*$. We have shown that $n_{c_a} = 1$ is a valid choice for every constant function c_a .

Definition 5.5. For $s \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}_+$, we define the set

$$\Phi_{s,n} := \{f \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(n)} \setminus s^* \mid \forall 1 \leq k < n \ \forall \beta: n \rightarrow k: \delta_\beta f \in s^*\}.$$

Lemma 5.6. For $s \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}_+$, it holds that

$$\Phi_{s,n} = \{f \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(n)} \setminus s^* \mid \forall 1 \leq i < j \leq n: \Delta_{ij} f \in s^*\}.$$

Proof. Recall that

$$\Delta_{ij} f(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}) := f(x_1, \dots, x_{j-1}, x_i, x_j, \dots, x_{n-1}).$$

“ $\subseteq$ ”: This inclusion is trivial because $\Delta_{ij} f$ is a variable identification of f with the corresponding variable identification map

$$\beta(k) = \begin{cases} k & \text{if } 1 \leq k < j, \\ i & \text{if } k = j, \\ k-1 & \text{if } j < k \leq n. \end{cases}$$

“ $\supseteq$ ”: Let $k \in \mathbb{N}_+$ such that $k < n$ and $\beta: \{1, \dots, n\} \rightarrow \{1 \dots k\}$. Let $f \in \{g \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(n)} \setminus s^* \mid \forall 1 \leq i < j \leq n: \Delta_{ij} g \in s^*\}$. The map β cannot be

5 WITNESS-COMPLETE SETS

injective because $k < n$. Hence, we know that there exist $i, j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ which satisfy $\beta(i) = \beta(j)$. Without loss of generality, we can assume that $i < j$. We know that $\Delta_{ij}f \in s^*$. Now we will define an $(n-1)$ -ary variable identification map $\tilde{\beta}: \{1, \dots, n-1\} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, k\}$ for $1 \leq l \leq n-1$ as follows:

$$\tilde{\beta}(l) = \begin{cases} \beta(l) & \text{if } l < j, \\ \beta(l+1) & \text{if } l \geq j. \end{cases}$$

With the help of variable identification map $\tilde{\beta}$, we can show that $\delta_{\tilde{\beta}}f$ is a variable identification of $\Delta_{ij}f$. Namely, for all $(x_1, \dots, x_k) \in A^k$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_{\tilde{\beta}}(\Delta_{ij}f)(x_1, \dots, x_k) &= \Delta_{ij}f(x_{\beta(1)}, \dots, x_{\beta(j-1)}, x_{\beta(j+1)}, \dots, x_{\beta(n)}) \\ &= f(x_{\beta(1)}, \dots, x_{\beta(j-1)}, x_{\beta(i)}, x_{\beta(j+1)}, \dots, x_{\beta(n)}) \\ &= f(x_{\beta(1)}, \dots, x_{\beta(j-1)}, x_{\beta(j)}, x_{\beta(j+1)}, \dots, x_{\beta(n)}) \\ &= \delta_{\beta}f(x_1, \dots, x_k). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\delta_{\tilde{\beta}}f \in s^*$ follows by Lemma 4.17 because $\delta_{\tilde{\beta}}f$ is a variable identification of $\Delta_{ij}f$ and $\Delta_{ij}f \in s^*$. $\square$

Theorem 5.7. *Let $(n_s)_{s \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)} \setminus \{\text{id}\}}$ be a tuple of positive integers such that n_s satisfies the condition in Lemma 5.3 for $s \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}$. Define*

$$\Phi_s := \bigcup_{k=1}^{n_s} \Phi_{s,k} \text{ for } s \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)}.$$

Then the set of operations

$$\Phi := \bigcup_{s \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)} \setminus \{\text{id}\}} \Phi_s$$

is witness-complete.

Proof. Once again, we will use a similar approach to the proof of Proposition 4.14. Let M be a centralizing monoid. We already know that M^* is a witness for M because $M^{**^{(1)}} = M$. Corollary 4.18 ensures that M^* is closed under variable identifications. Let $s \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)} \setminus M$. Every monoid contains the function id , hence we know that $s \neq \text{id}$. We want to find a function $f_s \in M^* \cap \Phi$ which does not commute with s .

Let $f_s \in M^*$ be of minimal arity n such that $f_s \not\perp s$. Note that such a function exists because $\forall f \in M^*: f \perp s$ would imply $s \in M^{**^{(1)}} = M$. Clearly, we have that $f_s \in M^* \setminus s^*$. Using Proposition 4.22 (i), we obtain that every variable identification of f_s belongs to s^* , which also can be expressed as

$$\forall 1 \leq k < n \forall \beta: n \rightarrow k: \delta_{\beta}f_s \in s^*.$$

5 WITNESS-COMPLETE SETS

We thus know that $f_s \in \Phi_{s,n}$. Therefore,

$$f_s \in \bigcup_{k=1}^{n_s} \Phi_{s,k} = \Phi_s \subseteq \Phi$$

follows immediately if we are able to show that $n \leq n_s$. Assume $n_s < n$. The set M^* is closed under variable identifications. Furthermore, it satisfies $M^* \not\subseteq s^*$ because $M^* \subseteq s^*$ would by Corollary 4.7 be equivalent to $s \in M^{**(1)} = M$. With the help of Lemma 5.3, it follows that

$$(M^*)^{\leq n_s} \not\subseteq s^*.$$

This means that there exists a $g \in M^*$ of arity $k \leq n_s$ such that $g \notin s^*$, and $g \notin s^*$ is equivalent to $g \not\subseteq s$. This contradicts the minimality of the arity of f_s . Hence, we know that $n \leq n_s$ and therefore also $f_s \in \Phi$. Analogously to the proof of Proposition 4.14, it follows that the set

$$\{f_s \mid s \in \mathcal{O}_A^{(1)} \setminus M\} \subseteq \Phi$$

is a witness for M . □

Definition 5.8. Let $f, g \in \mathcal{O}_A$. We call f and g *equivalent in the context of unary centralizers* if $f^{*(1)} = g^{*(1)}$. We will use the abbreviation $\sim$ to denote this relation:

$$f \sim g :\Leftrightarrow f^{*(1)} = g^{*(1)}.$$

This relation is obviously an equivalence relation.

Proposition 5.9. *Let $W \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$ be a witness-complete set of operations. Let $T \subseteq \mathcal{O}_A$ be a set of operations which satisfies the following condition:*

$$\forall f \in W \exists g \in T: f \sim g.$$

Then T is witness-complete.

Proof. Let M be a centralizing monoid and $S \subseteq W$ be a witness for M . Define the set

$$\tilde{S} := \{g \in T \mid \exists f \in S: f \sim g\} \subseteq T.$$

Since $S \subseteq W$, the assumption yields that for every $f \in S$ there is a $g \in T$ such that $f \sim g$, i.e., $f^{*(1)} = g^{*(1)}$. By the definition of $\tilde{S}$, such a g belongs to $\tilde{S}$. Therefore, we have

$$S^{*(1)} = \bigcap_{f \in S} f^{*(1)} \supseteq \bigcap_{g \in \tilde{S}} g^{*(1)} = \tilde{S}^{*(1)}.$$

Conversely, by the the definition of $\tilde{S}$, for every $g \in \tilde{S}$ there is some $f \in S$ such that $f^{*(1)} = g^{*(1)}$. We obtain that

$$\tilde{S}^{*(1)} = \bigcap_{g \in \tilde{S}} g^{*(1)} \supseteq \bigcap_{f \in S} f^{*(1)} = S^{*(1)}.$$

Hence, we know that $M = S^{*(1)} = \tilde{S}^{*(1)}$, which precisely means that $\tilde{S} \subseteq T$ is a witness for M . □

6 Centralizing monoids on a three-element set

In this section, we will computationally identify every centralizing monoid on the three-element set $A = \{0, 1, 2\} = 3$. By using the results of the previous section, we will construct a sufficiently small set of operations W , which is witness-complete. Afterwards, we will compute the concept lattice of the formal context $(W, \mathcal{O}_3^{(1)}, \perp)$. Because of Proposition 5.2, we know that the set of all intents of the context $(W, \mathcal{O}_3^{(1)}, \perp)$ equals the set of all centralizing monoids on A . The extent of a concept is a witness for the corresponding centralizing monoid.

Remark 5.4 ensures that $n_s = 3$ for $s \notin \{\text{id}, c_0, c_1, c_2\}$ and $n_{c_i} = 1$ for $i \in \{0, 1, 2\}$ is a valid tuple for Theorem 5.7. Recall that c_i denotes the constant function $c_i(x) = i$ for every $x \in \{0, 1, 2\}$. We thus know that the set

$$\Phi = \bigcup_{s \in \mathcal{O}_3^{(1)} \setminus \{\text{id}\}} \Phi_s,$$

where

$$\Phi_s = \bigcup_{k=1}^{n_s} \Phi_{s,k} \text{ for } s \in \mathcal{O}_3^{(1)}$$

and

$$\Phi_{s,n} = \{f \in \mathcal{O}_3^{(n)} \setminus s^* \mid \forall 1 \leq k < n \forall \beta: n \rightarrow k: \delta_\beta f \in s^*\},$$

is a witness-complete set of operations. Note that the set Φ_{c_i} for $i \in \{0, 1, 2\}$ contains only unary functions because $n_{c_i} = 1$, and $\Phi_{s,n}$ contains only n -ary functions. Hence, the following inclusion holds:

$$\Phi \subseteq \mathcal{O}_3^{(1)} \cup \mathcal{O}_3^{(2)} \cup \bigcup_{s \in \mathcal{O}_3^{(1)} \setminus \{\text{id}, c_0, c_1, c_2\}} \Phi_{s,3}.$$

Every superset of Φ obviously also contains a witness for every centralizing monoid. For every $s \in \mathcal{O}_3^{(1)}$, the binary operation $g(x, y) := s(x)$ clearly is equivalent to s in the context of unary centralizers. Therefore, we know that

$$\forall s \in \mathcal{O}_3^{(1)} \exists g \in \mathcal{O}_3^{(2)}: s \sim g.$$

Hence, it follows by Proposition 5.9 that the set

$$W := \mathcal{O}_3^{(2)} \cup \bigcup_{s \in \mathcal{O}_3^{(1)} \setminus \{\text{id}, c_0, c_1, c_2\}} \Phi_{s,3}$$

is witness-complete.

6 CENTRALIZING MONOIDS ON A THREE-ELEMENT SET

A superset of this set of operations W will be used to compute every centralizing monoid. But first, we will examine the set $\Phi_{s,3}$ for an arbitrary $s \in \mathcal{O}_3^{(1)}$. For $f \in \Phi_{s,3}$, we define the following binary operations:

$$\begin{aligned} g_1(x, y) &:= \Delta_{1,2}f(x, y) = f(x, x, y) \\ g_2(x, y) &:= \Delta_{1,3}f(x, y) = f(x, y, x) \\ g_3(x, y) &:= \Delta_{2,3}f(x, y) = f(x, y, y) \end{aligned}$$

These binary operations are variable identifications of f and hence, we know that $g_1, g_2, g_3 \in s^*$. Furthermore, these operations have to be compatible on the diagonal:

$$f(x, x, x) = g_1(x, x) = g_2(x, x) = g_3(x, x) \text{ for } x \in \{0, 1, 2\}.$$

By reversing this process, we obtain an algorithm which enumerates at least every $f \in \Phi_{s,3}$ and possibly some additional operations in $s^{*(3)}$:

- (1) Compute $s^{*(2)}$
- (2) Find compatible operations $g_1, g_2, g_3 \in s^{*(2)}$
- (3) Save every function f which equals g_1, g_2, g_3 for every non-injective tuple
- (4) Return to step two

Lemma 5.6 ensures that this algorithm computes a superset of $\Phi_{3,s}$. Step (3) can be implemented by assigning every possible value to f on every injective tuple. There are $3! = 6$ injective tuples in A^3 and 3 possible values per tuple, hence this step can be computed easily. In step (3) in the implementation of the algorithm, we will also check whether f is equivalent in the context of unary centralizers to a function which has already been stored and only save f if this is not the case. This is valid because we know that the final set still contains a witness for every centralizing monoid by Proposition 5.9. The amount of saved functions is drastically reduced by this extra step.

This algorithm has a reasonable run-time because the set $s^{*(2)}$ is small for $s \in \mathcal{O}_3^{(1)} \setminus \{\text{id}, c_0, c_1, c_2\}$. The set $\mathcal{O}_3^{(2)}$ has $3^9 = 19683$ elements. The identity commutes with every function. Every constant function c_i commutes with one third of the functions in $\mathcal{O}_3^{(2)}$ because for $f \in \mathcal{O}_3^{(2)}$, it holds that $f \perp c_i$ if and only if $f(i, i) = i$. This condition is satisfied by one third of the functions in $\mathcal{O}_3^{(2)}$, hence we know that $|c_i^{*(2)}| = 6561$. For $s \in \mathcal{O}_3^{(1)}$, the set $s^{*(2)}$ can be easily computed by simply checking whether s and f commute for every $f \in \mathcal{O}_3^{(2)}$. It turns out that $|s^{*(2)}| \leq 162$ for every $s \in \mathcal{O}_3^{(1)} \setminus \{\text{id}, c_0, c_1, c_2\}$. Therefore, a superset of the set $\Phi_{s,3}$ can be computed efficiently for $s \in \mathcal{O}_3^{(1)} \setminus \{\text{id}, c_0, c_1, c_2\}$ by the algorithm presented in

the previous paragraph and we do not need to compute $\Phi_{\text{id},3}$ or $\Phi_{c_i,3}$ for $i \in \{0, 1, 2\}$ because they are explicitly not included in the set W .

By using this algorithm to compute a superset of $\Phi_{s,3}$, we can outline the strategy to compute every centralizing monoid on $\{0, 1, 2\}$. The first step is to determine the objects of the formal context. This can be achieved by computing a superset of $\Phi_{s,3}$ for every $s \in \mathcal{O}_3^{(1)} \setminus \{\text{id}, c_0, c_1, c_2\}$. Furthermore, we add $\mathcal{O}_3^{(2)}$ to this set to obtain a superset of W . To reduce the size of the formal context, we will only use one object per equivalence class, i.e., if multiple functions have identical intents, we will only save one of those functions. This method results in 183 objects, which are listed in Appendix 7.2. The next step is to compute the formal context by simply checking if the objects and the attributes commute. The attributes of this context are the 27 unary functions on $\{0, 1, 2\}$. The entire C++ code which was used to compute this formal context can be found in Appendix 7.1. The context obtained by this method and the corresponding standard context are given in Appendix 7.3 and 7.4, respectively.

In the final step, we calculate the concept lattice of this formal context, row reduce it and compute the corresponding standard context, which consists of 51 objects and 25 attributes. We will not cover these steps in this thesis because there already exists software for manipulating formal contexts and computing concept lattices. For further details on how to determine a concept lattice, we refer to [3] and [4]. In this thesis, the ConExp software [10], which is presented in [11], and the ConExp-clj software [2] have been used to compute the standard context and the concept lattice of this formal context. The number of concepts in this formal context is 192, which matches the 192 centralizing monoids reported in [5]. A full list of all 192 centralizing monoids and corresponding witnesses is given in Appendix 7.5.

7 Appendix

7.1 C++ code

```

#include <iostream>
#include <fstream>
#include <set>
#include <vector>
using namespace std;

int main() {
vector<int> s(3,0);
//unary operation
//attributes in context of unary centralizers

vector<int> h(9,0);
//binary operation to compute s^(2)
//h(x,y)= h[x+3*y] for x,y=0,1,2

vector<int> f(27,0);
//ternary operation
//f(x,y,z)=f[x+3*y+9*z] for x,y,z=0,1,2

vector<int> g_1(9,0);
vector<int> g_2(9,0);
vector<int> g_3(9,0);
//g_1,g_2,g_3 \in s^(2) are binary building blocks for f

vector<int> r(3,0);
//unary operation

set< vector<int> > s_centralizer;
//set which contains s^(2)
//contains binary functions
//functions stored as vectors of length 9
//h(x,y)= h[x+3*y] for x,y=0,1,2

set< vector<int>> ternary_objects;
//ternary objects of the final subcontext of unary centralizers
//stores one function per equivalence class
//functions stored as vectors of length 27
//f(x,y,z)= f[x+3*y+9*z] for x,y,z=0,1,2

set< vector<int>> binary_objects;

```

7 APPENDIX

```
//binary objects of the final subcontext of unary centralizers
//stores one function per equivalence class
//functions stored as vectors of length 9
//h(x,y)= h[x+3*y] for x,y=0,1,2

set< vector<bool>> phi_intents;
//stores intents of functions in phi
//used to check whether two functions are equivalent
//i.e., have the same intent

vector<bool> f_intent(27,true);
//contains intent for a ternary operation f
//f_intent[r[2]+3*r[1]+9*r[0]]=true if f and r commute
//i.e., r is in the intent of f

vector<bool> h_intent(27,true);
//contains intent for a binary operation h
//h_intent[r[2]+3*r[1]+9* r[0]]=true if h and r commute
//i.e., r is in the intent of h

bool commute=true;

//calculate the intent of binary function
//store them in the set binary_objects
for(h[0]=0; h[0]<3;h[0]++)
for(h[1]=0; h[1]<3;h[1]++)
for(h[2]=0; h[2]<3;h[2]++)
for(h[3]=0; h[3]<3;h[3]++)
for(h[4]=0; h[4]<3;h[4]++)
for(h[5]=0; h[5]<3;h[5]++)
for(h[6]=0; h[6]<3;h[6]++)
for(h[7]=0; h[7]<3;h[7]++)
for(h[8]=0; h[8]<3;h[8]++) {

    //compute h^(1)
    for(r[0]=0; r[0]<3; r[0]++)
    for(r[1]=0; r[1]<3; r[1]++)
    for(r[2]=0; r[2]<3; r[2]++){

        //check if h and r commute
        commute=true;
        for(int i=0; i<3; i++){
            for (int j = 0; j < 3; j++) {
```

7 APPENDIX

```

        if( r[ h[i+3*j] ] != h[ r[i]+3*r[j] ] ){
            commute=false;
            break;
        }
    }
    if(!commute) break;
}

//h_intent[r[2]+3*r[1]+9*r[0]]=true if h and r commute
//i.e., r is in the intent of h
h_intent[ r[2]+ 3*r[1] + 9* r[0] ] = commute;

}

//set.insert() returns a pair
//set.insert().second accesses second member of the pair
//second member equals true if element was actually inserted
//False otherwise

//check if the intent of h is already in phi_intents
//if h has a new intent:
//h is added to the set binary_objects
if( phi_intents.insert(h_intent).second ){
    binary_objects.insert(h);
}
}

//calculate ternary objects of the context
//store them in the set ternary_objects
for(s[0]=0; s[0]<3; s[0]++){
for(s[1]=0; s[1]<3; s[1]++){
for(s[2]=0; s[2]<3; s[2]++){

    //check if s is constant or id
    if(s[0]==s[1] && s[1]==s[2]) continue;
    if(s[0]==0 && s[1]==1 && s[2]==2) continue;

    //compute s^(2)
    //check if s commutes with binary function h
    for(h[0]=0; h[0]<3;h[0]++)
    for(h[1]=0; h[1]<3;h[1]++)
    for(h[2]=0; h[2]<3;h[2]++)
    for(h[3]=0; h[3]<3;h[3]++)

```

7 APPENDIX

```

for(h[4]=0; h[4]<3;h[4]++)
for(h[5]=0; h[5]<3;h[5]++)
for(h[6]=0; h[6]<3;h[6]++)
for(h[7]=0; h[7]<3;h[7]++)
for(h[8]=0; h[8]<3;h[8]++){

    //check if h and s commute
    commute=true;
    for(int i=0; i<3; i++) {
        for (int j = 0; j < 3; j++) {
            if (s[h[i+3*j]] != h[s[i]+3*s[j]]){
                commute = false;
                break;
            }
        }
        if(!commute) break;
    }

    if(commute){
        s_centralizer.insert(h);
    }
}

//iterate over binary functions g_1, g_2, g_2 in s^(2)
//and check if they are compatible
//iterator has to be de-referenced
//Hence, g_1=*itr is used

//g_i(x,y)=g_i[x+3*y]
//g_i(0,0)=g_i[0]
//g_i(1,1)=g_i[4]
//g_i(2,2)=g_i[8]
for(set<vector<int>>::iterator itr_1=s_centralizer.begin();
itr_1 != s_centralizer.end();
itr_1++){

    g_1=*itr_1;
    for(set<vector<int>>::iterator itr_2=s_centralizer.begin();
itr_2 != s_centralizer.end();
itr_2++){

        g_2=*itr_2;
        if(!((g_1[0]==g_2[0])&&(g_1[4]==g_2[4])&&(g_1[8]==g_2[8]))) {
            continue;
        }
    }
}

```

7 APPENDIX

```

}

for(set<vector<int>>::iterator itr_3=s_centralizer.begin();
itr_3 != s_centralizer.end();
itr_3++){

    g_3=*itr_3;
    if(!((g_1[0]==g_3[0])&&(g_1[4]==g_3[4])&&(g_1[8]==g_3[8]))){
        continue;
    }

    //build every possible ternary function f
    //which equals g_1,g_2,g_3 for every non-injective tuple
    //f(x,y,z) = f[x+3*y+9*z]
    //f[0] = f(0,0,0) = g_i(0,0) = g_i[0]
    //f[1] = f(1,0,0) = g_3(1,0) = g_3[1]
    //f[2] = f(2,0,0) = g_3(2,0) = g_3[2]
    //f[3] = f(0,1,0) = g_2(0,1) = g_2[3]
    //f[4] = f(1,1,0) = g_1(1,0) = g_1[1]
    //f[5] = f(2,1,0)
    //f[6] = f(0,2,0) = g_2(0,2) = g_2[6]
    //f[7] = f(1,2,0)
    //f[8] = f(2,2,0) = g_1(2,0) = g_1[2]
    //f[9] = f(0,0,1) = g_1(0,1) = g_1[3]
    //f[10] = f(1,0,1) = g_2(1,0) = g_2[1]
    //f[11] = f(2,0,1)
    //f[12] = f(0,1,1) = g_3(0,1) = g_3[3]
    //f[13] = f(1,1,1) = g_i(1,1) = g_i[4]
    //f[14] = f(2,1,1) = g_3(2,1) = g_3[5]
    //f[15] = f(0,2,1)
    //f[16] = f(1,2,1) = g_2(1,2) = g_2[7]
    //f[17] = f(2,2,1) = g_1(2,1) = g_1[5]
    //f[18] = f(0,0,2) = g_1(0,2) = g_1[6]
    //f[19] = f(1,0,2)
    //f[20] = f(2,0,2) = g_2(2,0) = g_2[2]
    //f[21] = f(0,1,2)
    //f[22] = f(1,1,2) = g_1(1,2) = g_1[7]
    //f[23] = f(2,1,2) = g_2(2,1) = g_2[5]
    //f[24] = f(0,2,2) = g_3(0,2) = g_3[6]
    //f[25] = f(1,2,2) = g_3(1,2) = g_3[7]
    //f[26] = f(2,2,2) = g_i(2,2) = g_i[8]

    //set values for f
    f[0] = g_1[0];

```

7 APPENDIX

```
f[1] = g_3[1];
f[2] = g_3[2];
f[3] = g_2[3];
f[4] = g_1[1];
//f[5] injective tuple
f[6] = g_2[6];
//f[7] injective tuple
f[8] = g_1[2];
f[9] = g_1[3];
f[10] = g_2[1];
//f[11] injective tuple
f[12] = g_3[3];
f[13] = g_1[4];
f[14] = g_3[5];
//f[15] injective tuple
f[16] = g_2[7];
f[17] = g_1[5];
f[18] = g_1[6];
//f[19] injective tuple
f[20] = g_2[2];
//f[21] injective tuple
f[22] = g_1[7];
f[23] = g_2[5];
f[24] = g_3[6];
f[25] = g_3[7];
f[26] = g_1[8];

//iterate over every value for injective tuples
for(f[5]=0; f[5]<3; f[5]++)
for(f[7]=0; f[7]<3; f[7]++)
for(f[11]=0; f[11]<3; f[11]++)
for(f[15]=0; f[15]<3; f[15]++)
for(f[19]=0; f[19]<3; f[19]++)
for(f[21]=0; f[21]<3; f[21]++){

    //compute f^(1)
    for(r[0]=0; r[0]<3; r[0]++)
    for(r[1]=0; r[1]<3; r[1]++)
    for(r[2]=0; r[2]<3; r[2]++){

        //check if f and r commute
        //r is a unary function
        commute=true;
        for(int i=0; i<3; i++){
```

7 APPENDIX

```

for(int j=0; j<3; j++){
for(int k=0; k<3; k++){
    if(r[f[i+3*j+9*k]]!=f[r[i]+3*r[j]+9*r[k]]){
        commute=false;
        break;
    }
}
if(!commute) break;
}
if(!commute) break;
}

//f_intent[r[2]+3*r[1]+9*r[0]]=true
//if f and r commute
//i.e., r is in the intent of f
f_intent[ r[2]+ 3*r[1] + 9* r[0] ] = commute;

}

//check if the intent of f is in phi_intents
//if f has a new intent:
//f is added to the set ternary_objects
if( phi_intents.insert(f_intent).second){
ternary_objects.insert(f);
}
}
}

//output size of s^(2)
cout<< "Size of s*(2) for s="
<< s[0] << s[1] << s[2] << ":      "
<< s_centralizer.size() << endl;

//clear the set s^(2) before the next iteration
s_centralizer.clear();
}

//compute the formal context of unary centralizers
//ternary_objects and binary_objects as objects
//unary functions as attributes
//context will be stored in "context_of_unary_centralizers.txt"

```

7 APPENDIX

```
//simply called "table" in c++ code
fstream table;
table.open("context_of_unary_centralizers", ios::out);

//write down all objects and then all attributes in the table
//functions will be written as vectors
//h(x,y)=h[x+3*y]
//f(x,y,z)=f[x+3*y+9*z]

//binary_objects
for(set<vector<int>>::iterator itr=binary_objects.begin();
    itr != binary_objects.end();
    itr++){

    h=*itr;
    for (int i = 0; i < 9; i++){
        table << h[i];
    }
    table << endl;
}

//ternary objects
for(set<vector<int>>::iterator itr=ternary_objects.begin();
    itr != ternary_objects.end();
    itr++){

    f=*itr;
    for (int i = 0; i < 27; i++){
        table << f[i];
    }
    table << endl;
}

//attributes, i.e., unary functions
for(s[0]=0; s[0]<3; s[0]++)
for(s[1]=0; s[1]<3; s[1]++)
for(s[2]=0; s[2]<3; s[2]++) {
    table << s[0] << s[1] << s[2] << endl;
}

//adding the commutation relation to the table
//rows in the same order as the objects listed above

//binary objects
```

7 APPENDIX

```

for(set<vector<int>>::iterator itr = binary_objects.begin();
    itr != binary_objects.end();
    itr++) {

    h = *itr;

    for (r[0] = 0; r[0] < 3; r[0]++)
    for (r[1] = 0; r[1] < 3; r[1]++)
    for (r[2] = 0; r[2] < 3; r[2]++) {

        //check if h and r commute
        commute = true;
        for (int i = 0; i < 3; i++) {
        for (int j = 0; j < 3; j++) {
            if (r[h[i+3*j]] != h[r[i]+3*r[j]]) {
                commute = false;
                break;
            }
        }
        if (!commute) break;
    }

    //Write X in table if h and r commute
    if (commute) {
        table << "X";
    } else {
        table << " ";
    }
}
table << endl;
}

//ternary objects
for(set<vector<int>>::iterator itr=ternary_objects.begin();
    itr != ternary_objects.end();
    itr++){

    f=*itr;

    for(r[0]=0; r[0]<3; r[0]++)
    for(r[1]=0; r[1]<3; r[1]++)
    for(r[2]=0; r[2]<3; r[2]++){

        //check if f and r commute

```

7 APPENDIX

```
    commute=true;
    for(int i=0; i<3; i++){
    for (int j = 0; j < 3; j++) {
    for (int k = 0; k < 3; k++) {
        if(r[f[i+3*j+9*k]]!= f[r[i]+3*r[j]+9*r[k]]){
            commute=false;
            break;
        }
    }
    if(!commute) break;
    }
    if(!commute) break;
    }

    //Write X in table if f and r commute
    if (commute) {
        table << "X";
    } else {
        table << " ";
    }
    }
    table << endl;
}

table.close();
return 0;
}
```

7.2 Object and attribute abbreviations

In the C++ program and output, functions are saved as vectors. Writing down a function as a vector is rather impractical because it takes a lot of space. Hence, we will use abbreviations for the objects and attributes of the context we computed.

The attributes of the context are simply all unary functions. The vector representation of a unary function s is given by $s(x) = s[x]$ for $x \in \{0, 1, 2\}$. Hence, we can denote $s \in \mathcal{O}_3^{(1)}$ by s_i for $i = 9 \cdot s[0] + 3 \cdot s[1] + s[2]$, i.e., the column of the attribute s is the i -th column of the context. The first index is 0. By using this abbreviation, the set of all attributes can be denoted by $\{s_0, s_1, \dots, s_{26}\}$.

The objects of the context are only a small subset of the binary and ternary operations on $\{0, 1, 2\}$. Each binary object will be abbreviated as h_i such that $i \in \mathbb{N}$ equals the row of the object. The first index is 0. The vector representation of a binary function is given by $h(x, y) = h[x + 3 \cdot y]$ for $x, y \in \{0, 1, 2\}$. Similarly, every ternary object will be abbreviated f_i such that $i \in \mathbb{N}$ equals the row of the object. The vector representation of a ternary function is given by $f(x, y, z) = f[x + 3 \cdot y + 9 \cdot z]$ for $x, y, z \in \{0, 1, 2\}$. A list of the object abbreviations is given below.

7 APPENDIX

$h_0 := 00000000$	$h_1 := 00000001$	$h_2 := 00000002$	$h_3 := 00000010$
$h_4 := 00000012$	$h_5 := 00000020$	$h_6 := 00000021$	$h_7 := 00000022$
$h_8 := 00000102$	$h_9 := 00000200$	$h_{10} := 00000220$	$h_{11} := 00000222$
$h_{12} := 00001020$	$h_{13} := 00001220$	$h_{14} := 00001222$	$h_{15} := 00001000$
$h_{16} := 00001001$	$h_{17} := 00001002$	$h_{18} := 00001010$	$h_{19} := 00001012$
$h_{20} := 00001020$	$h_{21} := 00001022$	$h_{22} := 000010102$	$h_{23} := 000010122$
$h_{24} := 000010202$	$h_{25} := 000010222$	$h_{26} := 000011011$	$h_{27} := 000011012$
$h_{28} := 000011021$	$h_{29} := 000011022$	$h_{30} := 000011111$	$h_{31} := 000011112$
$h_{32} := 000011222$	$h_{33} := 000012022$	$h_{34} := 000012222$	$h_{35} := 000020000$
$h_{36} := 000021012$	$h_{37} := 000022022$	$h_{38} := 000022222$	$h_{39} := 000100100$
$h_{40} := 000100200$	$h_{41} := 000101220$	$h_{42} := 000110002$	$h_{43} := 000110202$
$h_{44} := 000110222$	$h_{45} := 000111000$	$h_{46} := 000111002$	$h_{47} := 000111012$
$h_{48} := 000111020$	$h_{49} := 000111022$	$h_{50} := 000111102$	$h_{51} := 000111111$
$h_{52} := 000111112$	$h_{53} := 000111121$	$h_{54} := 000111122$	$h_{55} := 000111202$
$h_{56} := 000111212$	$h_{57} := 000111222$	$h_{58} := 000112112$	$h_{59} := 000112212$
$h_{60} := 000121212$	$h_{61} := 000121222$	$h_{62} := 000200200$	$h_{63} := 000210002$
$h_{64} := 000210222$	$h_{65} := 000211122$	$h_{66} := 000211212$	$h_{67} := 000211222$
$h_{68} := 000212022$	$h_{69} := 000212222$	$h_{70} := 001011222$	$h_{71} := 001110222$
$h_{72} := 001111012$	$h_{73} := 001111222$	$h_{74} := 001211202$	$h_{75} := 002010202$
$h_{76} := 002012222$	$h_{77} := 002111002$	$h_{78} := 002111022$	$h_{79} := 002112002$
$h_{80} := 002112012$	$h_{81} := 002210202$	$h_{82} := 002212022$	$h_{83} := 002212222$
$h_{84} := 010110002$	$h_{85} := 010110102$	$h_{86} := 010111112$	$h_{87} := 010212012$
$h_{88} := 011111112$	$h_{89} := 011111122$	$h_{90} := 011111212$	$h_{91} := 011111222$
$h_{92} := 011112122$	$h_{93} := 011211112$	$h_{94} := 011212122$	$h_{95} := 012210012$
$h_{96} := 012211212$	$h_{97} := 012211222$	$h_{98} := 012212012$	$h_{99} := 012212212$
$h_{100} := 012212222$	$h_{101} := 021210102$	$h_{102} := 022212222$	$h_{103} := 100000000$
$h_{104} := 100000001$	$h_{105} := 100000002$	$h_{106} := 100010000$	$h_{107} := 100010002$
$h_{108} := 100011011$	$h_{109} := 100011012$	$h_{110} := 100011021$	$h_{111} := 100011022$
$h_{112} := 100011111$	$h_{113} := 100011112$	$h_{114} := 100011222$	$h_{115} := 100012021$
$h_{116} := 100012221$	$h_{117} := 100021012$	$h_{118} := 100100100$	$h_{119} := 100101012$
$h_{120} := 100110220$	$h_{121} := 100111221$	$h_{122} := 100111222$	$h_{123} := 100121220$
$h_{124} := 100211121$	$h_{125} := 101000101$	$h_{126} := 101010101$	$h_{127} := 101012121$
$h_{128} := 101022121$	$h_{129} := 101101101$	$h_{130} := 101111221$	$h_{131} := 101121121$
$h_{132} := 101212121$	$h_{133} := 111111111$	$h_{134} := 200000000$	$h_{135} := 200011012$
$h_{136} := 200012022$	$h_{137} := 200012222$	$h_{138} := 200021012$	$h_{139} := 200021022$
$h_{140} := 200022022$	$h_{141} := 200022222$	$h_{142} := 200100200$	$h_{143} := 200101202$
$h_{144} := 200111022$	$h_{145} := 200111222$	$h_{146} := 200121222$	$h_{147} := 202022222$
$h_{148} := 220220000$	$h_{149} := 220220002$	$h_{150} := 220220220$	$h_{151} := 220221011$
$h_{152} := 220221012$	$h_{153} := 220221112$	$h_{154} := 220221221$	$h_{155} := 222222222$

7 APPENDIX

$f_{156} := 000000000000010000000000222$ $f_{157} := 000000000000011011000011022$
 $f_{158} := 000000000000011011000011222$ $f_{159} := 000000000000011011000111012$
 $f_{160} := 000000000000012022000022222$ $f_{161} := 000000000000012022000222022$
 $f_{162} := 0000000000000100100000100200$ $f_{163} := 0000000000000111111000111112$
 $f_{164} := 0000000000000111111000211222$ $f_{165} := 0000000000000111122000122222$
 $f_{166} := 0000000000000212222000222222$ $f_{167} := 000010002010111012002012222$
 $f_{168} := 000011012011111112012112222$ $f_{169} := 000012022012111212022212222$
 $f_{170} := 000100200100111121200121222$ $f_{171} := 000100200100111121200221222$
 $f_{172} := 000100200100211121200121122$ $f_{173} := 000100220100111221220221222$
 $f_{174} := 000100220101111221220221222$ $f_{175} := 000101200101111121200121222$
 $f_{176} := 000101200101111121220121222$ $f_{177} := 001100220100110220220220222$
 $f_{178} := 002101200101012121200121222$ $f_{179} := 002102220102012221220221222$
 $f_{180} := 012101210101210101210101012$ $f_{181} := 101000101000012022101022121$
 $f_{182} := 220220000220221011000011012$

7.3 Output context

$\perp$	s_0	s_1	s_2	s_3	s_4	s_5	s_6	s_7	s_8	s_9	s_{10}	s_{11}	s_{12}	s_{13}	s_{14}	s_{15}	s_{16}	s_{17}	s_{18}	s_{19}	s_{20}	s_{21}	s_{22}	s_{23}	s_{24}	s_{25}	s_{26}
h_0	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×																		
h_1	×	×				×																					
h_2	×		×	×		×																					×
h_3	×	×	×			×																					
h_4	×		×			×																					×
h_5	×			×		×	×																				
h_6	×					×																					
h_7	×			×		×																					×
h_8	×					×																					×
h_9	×			×		×																					
h_{10}	×		×	×		×																					
h_{11}	×		×	×		×																			×		×
h_{12}	×					×		×																			
h_{13}	×		×			×																					
h_{14}	×		×			×																			×		×
h_{15}	×		×	×		×								×													
h_{16}	×					×								×													
h_{17}	×	×	×	×		×	×	×						×													×
h_{18}	×		×			×								×													
h_{19}	×	×	×			×								×													×
h_{20}	×			×		×								×													

7 APPENDIX

$\perp$	s_0	s_1	s_2	s_3	s_4	s_5	s_6	s_7	s_8	s_9	s_{10}	s_{11}	s_{12}	s_{13}	s_{14}	s_{15}	s_{16}	s_{17}	s_{18}	s_{19}	s_{20}	s_{21}	s_{22}	s_{23}	s_{24}	s_{25}	s_{26}	
h_{21}	×			×		×	×							×													×	
h_{22}	×	×				×								×														×
h_{23}	×					×								×														×
h_{24}	×			×		×								×														×
h_{25}	×		×	×		×								×												×		×
h_{26}	×				×	×								×	×													
h_{27}	×	×	×		×	×			×					×	×			×										×
h_{28}	×				×	×								×														
h_{29}	×				×	×		×	×					×														×
h_{30}	×					×								×	×													
h_{31}	×	×				×								×	×													×
h_{32}	×		×			×								×	×											×	×	×
h_{33}	×			×	×	×	×		×					×										×	×			×
h_{34}	×			×		×								×									×		×			×
h_{35}	×					×	×																					
h_{36}	×					×			×																			×
h_{37}	×					×			×																×			×
h_{38}	×					×																			×			×
h_{39}	×				×	×																						
h_{40}	×				×	×		×	×																			
h_{41}	×	×	×	×		×	×	×																				
h_{42}	×		×			×								×														×
h_{43}	×					×		×						×														×
h_{44}	×	×	×			×							×	×												×		×
h_{45}	×		×	×		×					×			×														
h_{46}	×		×	×		×					×			×														×
h_{47}	×		×			×						×		×	×													×
h_{48}	×			×		×					×			×														
h_{49}	×			×		×					×			×			×								×			×
h_{50}	×					×						×		×														×
h_{51}	×				×	×			×					×	×													
h_{52}	×				×	×			×					×	×													×
h_{53}	×				×	×			×					×														
h_{54}	×				×	×			×					×				×						×				×
h_{55}	×			×		×	×				×			×								×						×
h_{56}	×				×	×			×	×				×					×									×
h_{57}	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×
h_{58}	×				×	×			×					×														×
h_{59}	×				×	×		×	×	×				×					×									×
h_{60}	×					×			×										×									×
h_{61}	×					×			×										×						×			×

7 APPENDIX

$\perp$	s_0	s_1	s_2	s_3	s_4	s_5	s_6	s_7	s_8	s_9	s_{10}	s_{11}	s_{12}	s_{13}	s_{14}	s_{15}	s_{16}	s_{17}	s_{18}	s_{19}	s_{20}	s_{21}	s_{22}	s_{23}	s_{24}	s_{25}	s_{26}	
h_{62}	×					×			×																			
h_{63}	×					×	×							×														×
h_{64}	×					×								×									×					×
h_{65}	×					×		×						×				×						×				×
h_{66}	×					×			×					×					×									×
h_{67}	×					×			×					×				×	×					×				×
h_{68}	×					×	×							×											×			×
h_{69}	×					×			×					×					×						×			×
h_{70}	×					×								×	×												×	×
h_{71}	×	×				×						×	×	×														×
h_{72}	×					×								×	×													×
h_{73}	×	×				×							×	×	×												×	×
h_{74}	×					×								×		×					×							×
h_{75}	×			×		×								×								×						×
h_{76}	×		×	×		×							×	×	×							×			×			×
h_{77}	×			×		×					×			×														×
h_{78}	×			×		×				×				×			×						×		×			×
h_{79}	×		×			×								×												×		×
h_{80}	×		×			×					×			×	×											×	×	×
h_{81}	×					×								×								×						×
h_{82}	×					×								×											×			×
h_{83}	×					×								×								×			×			×
h_{84}	×		×			×							×	×														×
h_{85}	×					×							×	×														×
h_{86}	×					×							×	×	×													×
h_{87}	×					×								×			×								×			×
h_{88}	×				×	×						×	×	×									×	×				×
h_{89}	×				×	×								×														×
h_{90}	×				×	×								×										×				×
h_{91}	×				×	×								×	×												×	×
h_{92}	×				×	×								×					×									×
h_{93}	×					×								×										×				×
h_{94}	×					×								×				×										×
h_{95}	×					×	×							×								×	×					×
h_{96}	×					×			×					×											×			×
h_{97}	×					×			×					×														×
h_{98}	×					×	×							×			×					×			×			×
h_{99}	×					×			×					×			×								×			×
h_{100}	×					×			×					×				×										×
h_{101}	×					×		×				×		×						×		×						×
h_{102}	×					×			×			×		×					×			×			×			×

7 APPENDIX

$\perp$	s_0	s_1	s_2	s_3	s_4	s_5	s_6	s_7	s_8	s_9	s_{10}	s_{11}	s_{12}	s_{13}	s_{14}	s_{15}	s_{16}	s_{17}	s_{18}	s_{19}	s_{20}	s_{21}	s_{22}	s_{23}	s_{24}	s_{25}	s_{26}	
h_{103}					×	×																						
h_{104}						×																						
h_{105}						×																						×
h_{106}						×								×														
h_{107}						×								×														×
h_{108}					×	×								×	×													
h_{109}					×	×								×	×													×
h_{110}					×	×								×														
h_{111}					×	×								×														×
h_{112}						×								×	×													
h_{113}						×								×	×													×
h_{114}						×								×	×												×	×
h_{115}					×	×								×										×				
h_{116}						×								×									×					
h_{117}						×													×									×
h_{118}					×	×				×																		
h_{119}						×						×																×
h_{120}						×							×	×														
h_{121}					×	×							×	×	×								×	×				
h_{122}					×	×								×	×												×	×
h_{123}						×										×					×							
h_{124}						×								×										×				
h_{125}				×		×																						
h_{126}				×		×								×														
h_{127}				×		×								×									×		×			
h_{128}						×																			×			
h_{129}				×		×					×																	
h_{130}						×							×	×	×													
h_{131}						×											×								×			
h_{132}						×								×											×			
h_{133}				×	×	×							×	×	×								×	×	×			
h_{134}						×				×																		
h_{135}						×				×				×														×
h_{136}						×				×				×											×			×
h_{137}						×								×											×			×
h_{138}						×				×									×									×
h_{139}						×				×																		×
h_{140}						×				×															×			×
h_{141}						×																			×			×
h_{142}						×				×										×								
h_{143}						×																×						×

7 APPENDIX

$\perp$	s_0	s_1	s_2	s_3	s_4	s_5	s_6	s_7	s_8	s_9	s_{10}	s_{11}	s_{12}	s_{13}	s_{14}	s_{15}	s_{16}	s_{17}	s_{18}	s_{19}	s_{20}	s_{21}	s_{22}	s_{23}	s_{24}	s_{25}	s_{26}	
h_{144}						×								×			×							×			×	
h_{145}						×			×					×			×								×			×
h_{146}						×			×			×							×			×			×			×
h_{147}						×																×			×			×
h_{148}			×			×																						
h_{149}			×			×																						×
h_{150}			×			×																				×		
h_{151}						×										×												
h_{152}			×			×						×				×												×
h_{153}						×										×												×
h_{154}						×										×											×	
h_{155}			×			×			×			×				×						×			×			×
f_{156}	×		×	×		×								×														×
f_{157}	×				×	×			×					×														×
f_{158}	×		×			×								×	×													×
f_{159}	×	×	×			×								×	×													×
f_{160}	×			×		×								×											×			×
f_{161}	×			×		×	×							×											×			×
f_{162}	×				×	×			×																			
f_{163}	×				×	×								×	×													×
f_{164}	×				×	×			×					×					×									×
f_{165}	×				×	×			×					×										×				×
f_{166}	×					×			×					×											×			×
f_{167}	×	×	×	×		×	×	×			×		×	×	×		×				×			×	×	×	×	×
f_{168}	×	×	×		×	×			×	×			×	×	×				×	×			×	×		×	×	×
f_{169}	×			×	×	×	×		×	×	×	×		×			×	×	×		×			×	×			×
f_{170}	×				×	×			×	×				×					×	×				×				×
f_{171}	×				×	×		×	×	×				×					×	×				×				×
f_{172}	×					×								×					×					×				×
f_{173}	×	×	×			×							×	×	×											×	×	×
f_{174}	×	×	×			×						×	×	×	×											×	×	×
f_{175}	×			×		×	×				×			×								×			×			×
f_{176}	×			×		×	×				×			×								×	×		×			×
f_{177}	×	×				×							×	×														×
f_{178}	×			×		×								×								×			×			×
f_{179}	×		×			×							×	×	×													×
f_{180}	×					×	×							×								×						×
f_{181}				×		×								×											×			
f_{182}			×			×									×													×

7 APPENDIX

7.4 Standard context

$\perp$	s_0	s_1	s_2	s_3	s_4	s_6	s_7	s_8	s_9	s_{10}	s_{11}	s_{12}	s_{13}	s_{14}	s_{15}	s_{16}	s_{17}	s_{18}	s_{20}	s_{21}	s_{22}	s_{23}	s_{24}	s_{25}	s_{26}
h_0	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x																	
h_{11}	x		x	x																			x		x
h_{17}	x	x	x	x		x	x					x													x
h_{25}	x		x	x								x											x		x
h_{27}	x	x	x		x			x				x	x				x								x
h_{29}	x				x		x	x				x													x
h_{33}	x			x	x	x		x				x									x	x			x
h_{34}	x			x								x								x		x			x
h_{44}	x	x	x									x	x										x		x
h_{45}	x		x	x						x		x													
h_{46}	x		x	x						x		x													x
h_{47}	x		x								x	x	x												x
h_{51}	x				x				x			x	x												
h_{52}	x				x				x			x	x												x
h_{54}	x				x				x			x					x				x				x
h_{55}	x			x		x				x		x													x
h_{59}	x				x		x	x	x			x						x							x
h_{61}	x							x										x				x			x
h_{65}	x						x					x					x					x			x
h_{67}	x							x				x					x	x				x			x
h_{69}	x							x				x						x					x		x
h_{71}	x	x									x	x	x												x
h_{73}	x	x										x	x	x										x	x
h_{74}	x											x			x					x					x
h_{76}	x		x	x								x	x	x									x		x
h_{78}	x			x						x		x				x					x		x		x
h_{80}	x		x								x	x	x										x	x	x
h_{88}	x				x							x	x	x							x	x			x
h_{91}	x				x							x	x											x	x
h_{95}	x					x						x									x				x
h_{98}	x					x						x				x							x		x
h_{99}	x							x				x				x							x		x
h_{101}	x						x				x	x			x				x	x					x
h_{102}	x							x			x	x					x						x		x
h_{118}					x				x																
h_{122}					x							x	x											x	x
h_{123}															x					x					
h_{129}				x						x															
h_{131}																x							x		

7 APPENDIX

$\perp$	s_0	s_1	s_2	s_3	s_4	s_6	s_7	s_8	s_9	s_{10}	s_{11}	s_{12}	s_{13}	s_{14}	s_{15}	s_{16}	s_{17}	s_{18}	s_{20}	s_{21}	s_{22}	s_{23}	s_{24}	s_{25}	s_{26}
h_{133}				×	×							×	×	×						×	×	×			
h_{142}								×										×							
h_{145}								×					×			×							×		×
h_{150}			×																				×		
h_{154}													×											×	
h_{155}			×					×			×			×			×						×		×
f_{167}	×	×	×	×		×	×			×		×	×	×		×						×	×	×	×
f_{168}	×	×	×		×			×	×			×	×	×			×	×		×	×		×	×	×
f_{169}	×			×	×	×		×	×	×	×		×			×	×	×				×	×		×
f_{171}	×			×		×	×	×	×			×					×	×				×			×
f_{174}	×	×	×								×	×	×	×									×	×	×
f_{176}	×			×		×				×			×			×						×		×	×

7.5 Centralizing monoids and corresponding witnesses

$$\begin{aligned}
& \{h_{129}, h_{17}, h_{118}, h_{91}, h_{88}, h_{34}, h_{123}, h_{102}, h_{54}, f_{169}, h_{46}, h_{150}, h_{59}, h_{67}, h_{95}, h_{101}, h_{154}, h_{55}, \\
& \quad h_{51}, h_{11}, h_{99}, h_{73}, h_{74}, h_{155}, h_{80}, h_{122}, h_{78}, h_{76}, h_{142}, h_{71}, h_{65}, h_{27}, h_{29}, h_{69}, h_0, h_{133}, f_{176}, \\
& \quad h_{44}, h_{98}, h_{47}, h_{131}, h_{45}, f_{167}, h_{145}, h_{52}, h_{25}, f_{168}, h_{33}, h_{61}, f_{174}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_5\} \\
& \{h_{123}, h_{101}, h_{74}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{15}, s_{19}, s_5\} \\
& \}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{15}, s_{20}, s_{22}, s_{14}, s_{10}, s_{19}, s_{21}, s_{13}, s_{25}, s_{17}, s_7, s_3, s_{16}, s_{18}, s_{11}, s_{12}, s_4, s_{23}, s_2, s_9, s_6, \\
& \quad s_{26}, s_0, s_{24}, s_8, s_1, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{101}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{15}, s_{19}, s_{21}, s_{13}, s_7, s_{11}, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{101}, h_{74}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{15}, s_{19}, s_{13}, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{102}, f_{169}, h_{95}, h_{55}, h_{155}, h_{76}, f_{176}, h_{98}, f_{167}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{20}, s_{26}, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{20}, s_{22}, s_{10}, s_{13}, s_{17}, s_3, s_{16}, s_{18}, s_{11}, s_4, s_{23}, s_9, s_6, \\
& \quad s_{26}, s_0, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{155}, h_{76}, f_{167}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{20}, s_{14}, s_{23}, s_2, s_{26}, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{167}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{20}, s_{14}, s_{10}, s_{13}, s_{25}, s_7, s_3, s_{16}, s_{12}, s_{23}, s_2, s_6, s_{26}, s_0, s_{24}, s_1, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{76}, f_{167}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{20}, s_{14}, s_{13}, s_3, s_{12}, s_{23}, s_2, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{155}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{20}, s_{14}, s_{17}, s_{11}, s_{23}, s_2, s_{26}, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, h_{55}, f_{176}, f_{167}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{20}, s_{10}, s_{13}, s_3, s_6, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{176}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{20}, s_{10}, s_{21}, s_{13}, s_3, s_{16}, s_{23}, s_6, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, f_{176}, f_{167}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{20}, s_{10}, s_{13}, s_3, s_{16}, s_{23}, s_6, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{95}, f_{176}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{20}, s_{21}, s_{13}, s_6, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{102}, f_{169}, h_{95}, h_{55}, h_{76}, f_{176}, h_{98}, f_{167}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{20}, s_{13}, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\}
\end{aligned}$$

7 APPENDIX

$$\begin{aligned}
& \{h_{102}, f_{169}\}^{*(1)} \\
&= \{s_{20}, s_{13}, s_{17}, s_{11}, s_{23}, s_{26}, s_0, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, h_{55}, h_{76}, f_{176}, f_{167}\}^{*(1)} \\
&= \{s_{20}, s_{13}, s_3, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, h_{76}, f_{176}, f_{167}\}^{*(1)} \\
&= \{s_{20}, s_{13}, s_3, s_{23}, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, f_{176}, h_{98}, f_{167}\}^{*(1)} \\
&= \{s_{20}, s_{13}, s_{16}, s_{23}, s_6, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{102}, f_{169}, h_{76}, f_{176}, h_{98}, f_{167}\}^{*(1)} \\
&= \{s_{20}, s_{13}, s_{23}, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, h_{95}, h_{55}, f_{176}, h_{98}, f_{167}\}^{*(1)} \\
&= \{s_{20}, s_{13}, s_6, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{102}, f_{169}, h_{155}\}^{*(1)} \\
&= \{s_{20}, s_{17}, s_{11}, s_{23}, s_{26}, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{102}, f_{169}, h_{155}, h_{76}, f_{176}, h_{98}, f_{167}\}^{*(1)} \\
&= \{s_{20}, s_{23}, s_{26}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{88}, h_{54}, f_{169}, h_{67}, h_{65}, h_{133}, f_{168}, h_{33}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
&= \{s_{22}, s_{13}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{88}, h_{133}, f_{168}\}^{*(1)} \\
&= \{s_{22}, s_{14}, s_{21}, s_{13}, s_{12}, s_4, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{168}\}^{*(1)} \\
&= \{s_{22}, s_{14}, s_{21}, s_{13}, s_{25}, s_{17}, s_{18}, s_{12}, s_4, s_2, s_9, s_{26}, s_0, s_{24}, s_8, s_1, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{133}\}^{*(1)} \\
&= \{s_{22}, s_{14}, s_{21}, s_{13}, s_3, s_{12}, s_4, s_{23}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{88}, f_{168}\}^{*(1)} \\
&= \{s_{22}, s_{14}, s_{21}, s_{13}, s_{12}, s_4, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{54}, f_{169}, h_{67}, h_{65}, f_{168}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
&= \{s_{22}, s_{13}, s_{17}, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{65}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
&= \{s_{22}, s_{13}, s_{17}, s_7, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
&= \{s_{22}, s_{13}, s_{17}, s_7, s_{18}, s_4, s_9, s_{26}, s_0, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, h_{67}, f_{168}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
&= \{s_{22}, s_{13}, s_{17}, s_{18}, s_{26}, s_0, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, f_{168}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
&= \{s_{22}, s_{13}, s_{17}, s_{18}, s_4, s_9, s_{26}, s_0, s_8, s_5\}
\end{aligned}$$

7 APPENDIX

$$\begin{aligned}
& \{h_{54}, f_{169}, f_{168}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{22}, s_{13}, s_{17}, s_4, s_9, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, h_{133}, h_{33}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{22}, s_{13}, s_3, s_4, s_{23}, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, h_{33}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{22}, s_{13}, s_3, s_4, s_{23}, s_6, s_{26}, s_0, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{88}, h_{54}, f_{169}, h_{133}, f_{168}, h_{33}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{22}, s_{13}, s_4, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{88}, h_{54}, f_{169}, f_{168}, h_{33}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{22}, s_{13}, s_4, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, f_{168}, h_{33}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{22}, s_{13}, s_4, s_{26}, s_0, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{88}, h_{54}, f_{169}, h_{67}, h_{65}, f_{168}, h_{33}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{22}, s_{13}, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, h_{67}, f_{168}, h_{33}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{22}, s_{13}, s_{26}, s_0, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{91}, h_{88}, h_{154}, h_{51}, h_{73}, h_{155}, h_{80}, h_{122}, h_{76}, h_{27}, h_{133}, h_{47}, f_{167}, h_{52}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{91}, h_{88}, h_{51}, h_{73}, h_{80}, h_{122}, h_{76}, h_{27}, h_{133}, h_{47}, f_{167}, h_{52}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{91}, h_{73}, h_{80}, h_{122}, f_{167}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_{25}, s_{26}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{80}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_{25}, s_{11}, s_2, s_{26}, s_0, s_{24}, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_{25}, s_{11}, s_{12}, s_2, s_{26}, s_0, s_{24}, s_1, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{73}, f_{167}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_{25}, s_{12}, s_{26}, s_0, s_1, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{167}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_{25}, s_{12}, s_2, s_{26}, s_0, s_{24}, s_1, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{91}, h_{122}, f_{168}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_{25}, s_4, s_{26}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{91}, f_{168}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_{25}, s_4, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{80}, f_{167}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_{25}, s_2, s_{26}, s_0, s_{24}, s_5\}
\end{aligned}$$

7 APPENDIX

$$\begin{aligned}
& \{h_{91}, h_{73}, h_{80}, f_{167}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_{25}, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{27}, f_{168}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_{17}, s_4, s_2, s_{26}, s_0, s_8, s_1, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{76}, h_{133}, f_{167}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_3, s_{12}, s_{23}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{80}, h_{47}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_{11}, s_2, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{88}, h_{73}, h_{76}, h_{133}, f_{167}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_{12}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{76}, f_{167}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_{12}, s_2, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{88}, h_{73}, h_{76}, f_{167}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_{12}, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{91}, h_{88}, h_{51}, h_{122}, h_{27}, h_{133}, h_{52}, f_{168}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_4, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{51}, h_{52}, f_{168}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_4, s_9, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{52}, f_{168}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_4, s_9, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{91}, h_{88}, h_{122}, h_{27}, h_{52}, f_{168}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_4, s_{26}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{91}, h_{88}, h_{27}, h_{52}, f_{168}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_4, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{91}, h_{88}, h_{51}, h_{27}, h_{52}, f_{168}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_4, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{80}, h_{76}, h_{27}, h_{47}, f_{167}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_2, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{27}, f_{167}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_2, s_{26}, s_0, s_1, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{91}, h_{88}, h_{73}, h_{80}, h_{122}, h_{76}, h_{27}, h_{47}, f_{167}, h_{52}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_{26}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{91}, h_{88}, h_{73}, h_{80}, h_{76}, h_{27}, h_{47}, f_{167}, h_{52}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{73}, h_{27}, f_{167}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_{26}, s_0, s_1, s_5\}
\end{aligned}$$

7 APPENDIX

$$\begin{aligned}
& \{h_{91}, h_{88}, h_{51}, h_{73}, h_{80}, h_{76}, h_{27}, h_{47}, f_{167}, h_{52}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{14}, s_{13}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{91}, h_{154}, h_{73}, h_{80}, h_{122}, f_{167}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{14}, s_{25}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{155}, h_{27}, f_{168}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{14}, s_{17}, s_2, s_{26}, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{155}, h_{80}, h_{47}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{14}, s_{11}, s_2, s_{26}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{155}, h_{76}, h_{133}, f_{167}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{14}, s_{23}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{155}, h_{80}, h_{76}, h_{27}, h_{47}, f_{167}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{14}, s_2, s_{26}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{91}, h_{88}, h_{73}, h_{155}, h_{80}, h_{122}, h_{76}, h_{27}, h_{47}, f_{167}, h_{52}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{14}, s_{26}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{129}, f_{169}, h_{46}, h_{55}, h_{78}, f_{176}, h_{45}, f_{167}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{10}, s_3, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{78}, f_{176}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{10}, s_{21}, s_{13}, s_3, s_{16}, s_{23}, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, h_{46}, h_{55}, h_{78}, f_{176}, h_{45}, f_{167}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{10}, s_{13}, s_3, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, h_{78}, f_{176}, f_{167}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{10}, s_{13}, s_3, s_{16}, s_{23}, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{46}, h_{45}, f_{167}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{10}, s_{13}, s_3, s_2, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{46}, f_{167}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{10}, s_{13}, s_3, s_2, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, h_{46}, h_{55}, h_{78}, f_{176}, f_{167}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{10}, s_{13}, s_3, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{88}, h_{34}, h_{95}, h_{101}, h_{78}, h_{133}, f_{176}, f_{168}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{21}, s_{13}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{34}, h_{78}, h_{133}, f_{176}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{21}, s_{13}, s_3, s_{23}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{34}, h_{78}, f_{176}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{21}, s_{13}, s_3, s_{23}, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{88}, h_{34}, h_{95}, h_{101}, h_{78}, f_{176}, f_{168}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{21}, s_{13}, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\}
\end{aligned}$$

7 APPENDIX

$$\begin{aligned}
& \{h_{17}, h_{91}, h_{88}, h_{34}, h_{102}, h_{54}, f_{169}, h_{46}, h_{59}, h_{67}, h_{95}, h_{101}, h_{55}, h_{51}, h_{99}, h_{73}, h_{74}, h_{80}, \\
& \quad h_{122}, h_{78}, h_{76}, h_{71}, h_{65}, h_{27}, h_{29}, h_{69}, h_{133}, f_{176}, h_{44}, h_{98}, h_{47}, h_{45}, f_{167}, h_{145}, h_{52}, h_{25}, \\
& \quad f_{168}, h_{33}, f_{174}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{13}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{102}, h_{54}, f_{169}, h_{67}, h_{65}, h_{27}, f_{168}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{13}, s_{17}, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{54}, f_{169}, h_{27}, f_{168}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{13}, s_{17}, s_4, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, h_{27}, f_{168}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{13}, s_{17}, s_4, s_{26}, s_0, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{102}, f_{169}, h_{67}, h_{27}, f_{168}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{13}, s_{17}, s_{26}, s_0, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, h_{59}, h_{101}, h_{65}, h_{29}, f_{167}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{13}, s_7, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, f_{167}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{13}, s_7, s_3, s_2, s_6, s_{26}, s_0, s_1, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{59}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{13}, s_7, s_{18}, s_4, s_9, s_{26}, s_0, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{59}, h_{29}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{13}, s_7, s_4, s_{26}, s_0, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, h_{34}, f_{169}, h_{46}, h_{55}, h_{78}, h_{76}, h_{133}, f_{176}, h_{45}, f_{167}, h_{25}, h_{33}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{13}, s_3, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{34}, f_{169}, h_{78}, h_{76}, h_{133}, f_{176}, f_{167}, h_{33}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{13}, s_3, s_{23}, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, f_{176}, f_{167}, h_{33}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{13}, s_3, s_{23}, s_6, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{34}, f_{169}, h_{78}, h_{76}, f_{176}, f_{167}, h_{33}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{13}, s_3, s_{23}, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, h_{46}, h_{76}, h_{45}, f_{167}, h_{25}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{13}, s_3, s_2, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, h_{46}, h_{76}, f_{167}, h_{25}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{13}, s_3, s_2, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{167}, h_{25}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{13}, s_3, s_2, s_{26}, s_0, s_{24}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, f_{169}, h_{55}, f_{176}, f_{167}, h_{33}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{13}, s_3, s_6, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\}
\end{aligned}$$

7 APPENDIX

$$\begin{aligned}
& \{h_{17}, h_{34}, f_{169}, h_{46}, h_{55}, h_{78}, h_{76}, f_{176}, f_{167}, h_{25}, h_{33}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_3, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, h_{34}, f_{169}, h_{46}, h_{55}, h_{78}, h_{76}, f_{176}, h_{45}, f_{167}, h_{25}, h_{33}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_3, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, h_{99}, h_{78}, f_{176}, h_{98}, f_{167}, h_{145}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_{16}, s_{23}, s_{26}, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, h_{99}, h_{78}, f_{176}, h_{98}, f_{167}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_{16}, s_{23}, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, h_{99}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_{16}, s_{23}, s_{26}, s_0, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, h_{99}, h_{145}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_{16}, s_{23}, s_{26}, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, h_{59}, h_{67}, h_{69}, f_{168}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_{18}, s_{26}, s_0, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, h_{59}, f_{168}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_{18}, s_4, s_9, s_{26}, s_0, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, h_{69}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_{18}, s_{23}, s_{26}, s_0, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{102}, f_{169}, h_{101}, h_{80}, h_{71}, h_{47}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_{11}, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{71}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_{11}, s_{12}, s_{26}, s_0, s_1, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{88}, h_{73}, h_{76}, h_{71}, h_{133}, h_{44}, f_{167}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_{12}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{76}, h_{44}, f_{167}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_{12}, s_2, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{44}, f_{167}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_{12}, s_2, s_{26}, s_0, s_{24}, s_1, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{88}, h_{73}, h_{76}, h_{71}, h_{44}, f_{167}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_{12}, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{73}, h_{71}, h_{44}, f_{167}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_{12}, s_{26}, s_0, s_1, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{91}, h_{88}, h_{54}, f_{169}, h_{59}, h_{51}, h_{122}, h_{27}, h_{29}, h_{133}, h_{52}, f_{168}, h_{33}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_4, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{54}, f_{169}, h_{59}, h_{51}, h_{52}, f_{168}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_4, s_9, s_0, s_5\}
\end{aligned}$$

7 APPENDIX

$$\begin{aligned}
& \{h_{54}, f_{169}, h_{59}, h_{52}, f_{168}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_4, s_9, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{91}, h_{88}, h_{54}, f_{169}, h_{59}, h_{122}, h_{27}, h_{29}, h_{52}, f_{168}, h_{33}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_4, s_{26}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{91}, h_{88}, h_{54}, f_{169}, h_{59}, h_{27}, h_{29}, h_{52}, f_{168}, h_{33}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_4, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, h_{59}, h_{27}, h_{29}, f_{168}, h_{33}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_4, s_{26}, s_0, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{91}, h_{88}, h_{54}, f_{169}, h_{59}, h_{51}, h_{27}, h_{29}, h_{52}, f_{168}, h_{33}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_4, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{34}, h_{102}, f_{169}, h_{99}, h_{78}, h_{76}, h_{69}, h_{133}, f_{176}, h_{98}, f_{167}, h_{145}, h_{33}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_{23}, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, f_{176}, h_{98}, f_{167}, h_{33}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_{23}, s_6, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{34}, h_{102}, f_{169}, h_{99}, h_{78}, h_{76}, h_{69}, f_{176}, h_{98}, f_{167}, h_{145}, h_{33}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_{23}, s_{26}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{34}, h_{102}, f_{169}, h_{99}, h_{78}, h_{76}, h_{69}, f_{176}, h_{98}, f_{167}, h_{33}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_{23}, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{102}, f_{169}, h_{99}, h_{69}, h_{33}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_{23}, s_{26}, s_0, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{102}, f_{169}, h_{99}, h_{69}, h_{145}, h_{33}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_{23}, s_{26}, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, h_{46}, h_{80}, h_{76}, h_{27}, h_{44}, h_{47}, h_{45}, f_{167}, h_{25}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_2, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, h_{46}, h_{80}, h_{76}, h_{27}, h_{44}, h_{47}, f_{167}, h_{25}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_2, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{80}, h_{44}, f_{167}, h_{25}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_2, s_{26}, s_0, s_{24}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, h_{27}, h_{44}, f_{167}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_2, s_{26}, s_0, s_1, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, f_{169}, h_{95}, h_{55}, f_{176}, h_{98}, f_{167}, h_{33}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_6, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, h_{91}, h_{88}, h_{34}, h_{102}, h_{54}, f_{169}, h_{46}, h_{59}, h_{67}, h_{95}, h_{101}, h_{55}, h_{99}, h_{73}, h_{74}, h_{80}, h_{122}, h_{78}, \\
& \quad h_{76}, h_{71}, h_{65}, h_{27}, h_{29}, h_{69}, f_{176}, h_{44}, h_{98}, h_{47}, f_{167}, h_{145}, h_{52}, h_{25}, f_{168}, h_{33}, f_{174}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{13}, s_{26}, s_5\}
\end{aligned}$$

7 APPENDIX

$$\begin{aligned}
& \{h_{17}, h_{91}, h_{88}, h_{34}, h_{102}, h_{54}, f_{169}, h_{46}, h_{59}, h_{67}, h_{95}, h_{101}, h_{55}, h_{99}, h_{73}, h_{74}, h_{80}, h_{78}, h_{76}, \\
& \quad h_{71}, h_{65}, h_{27}, h_{29}, h_{69}, f_{176}, h_{44}, h_{98}, h_{47}, f_{167}, h_{52}, h_{25}, f_{168}, h_{33}, f_{174}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{13}, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{102}, f_{169}, h_{59}, h_{67}, h_{99}, h_{27}, h_{29}, h_{69}, f_{168}, h_{33}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{13}, s_{26}, s_0, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, h_{73}, h_{71}, h_{27}, h_{44}, f_{167}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{13}, s_{26}, s_0, s_1, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{102}, f_{169}, h_{59}, h_{67}, h_{99}, h_{27}, h_{29}, h_{69}, h_{145}, f_{168}, h_{33}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{13}, s_{26}, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, h_{91}, h_{88}, h_{34}, h_{102}, h_{54}, f_{169}, h_{46}, h_{59}, h_{67}, h_{95}, h_{101}, h_{55}, h_{51}, h_{99}, h_{73}, h_{74}, h_{80}, h_{78}, \\
& \quad h_{76}, h_{71}, h_{65}, h_{27}, h_{29}, h_{69}, f_{176}, h_{44}, h_{98}, h_{47}, h_{45}, f_{167}, h_{52}, h_{25}, f_{168}, h_{33}, f_{174}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{13}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{102}, h_{54}, f_{169}, h_{67}, h_{155}, h_{65}, h_{27}, f_{168}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{17}, s_{26}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{102}, f_{169}, h_{67}, h_{155}, h_{27}, f_{168}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{17}, s_{26}, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, h_{59}, h_{101}, h_{65}, h_{29}, h_0, f_{167}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_7, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, h_0, f_{167}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_7, s_3, s_2, s_6, s_0, s_1, s_5\} \\
& \{h_0\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_7, s_3, s_4, s_2, s_6, s_0, s_8, s_1, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{59}, h_{29}, h_0, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_7, s_4, s_0, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{129}, h_{17}, h_{34}, f_{169}, h_{46}, h_{55}, h_{11}, h_{78}, h_{76}, h_0, h_{133}, f_{176}, h_{45}, f_{167}, h_{25}, h_{33}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_3, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, h_0, h_{133}, h_{33}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_3, s_4, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, h_0, h_{33}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_3, s_4, s_6, s_0, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, h_{46}, h_{11}, h_{76}, h_0, h_{45}, f_{167}, h_{25}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_3, s_2, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, h_{46}, h_{11}, h_{76}, f_{167}, h_{25}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_3, s_2, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{11}, f_{167}, h_{25}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_3, s_2, s_{26}, s_0, s_{24}, s_5\}
\end{aligned}$$

7 APPENDIX

$$\begin{aligned}
& \{h_{17}, f_{169}, h_{55}, h_0, f_{176}, f_{167}, h_{33}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_3, s_6, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, h_{34}, f_{169}, h_{46}, h_{55}, h_{11}, h_{78}, h_{76}, f_{176}, f_{167}, h_{25}, h_{33}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_3, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, h_{34}, f_{169}, h_{46}, h_{55}, h_{11}, h_{78}, h_{76}, h_0, f_{176}, h_{45}, f_{167}, h_{25}, h_{33}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_3, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, h_{99}, h_{78}, f_{176}, h_{98}, h_{131}, f_{167}, h_{145}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{16}, s_{23}, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, h_{59}, h_{67}, h_{142}, h_{69}, f_{168}, h_{61}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{18}, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, h_{69}, h_{61}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{18}, s_{23}, s_{26}, s_0, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, h_{59}, h_{67}, h_{69}, f_{168}, h_{61}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{18}, s_{26}, s_0, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{102}, f_{169}, h_{101}, h_{155}, h_{80}, h_{71}, h_{47}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{11}, s_{26}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{118}, h_{91}, h_{88}, h_{54}, f_{169}, h_{59}, h_{51}, h_{122}, h_{27}, h_{29}, h_0, h_{133}, h_{52}, f_{168}, h_{33}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_4, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{27}, h_0, f_{168}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_4, s_2, s_0, s_8, s_1, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{118}, h_{54}, f_{169}, h_{59}, h_{51}, h_{52}, f_{168}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_4, s_9, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{91}, h_{88}, h_{54}, f_{169}, h_{59}, h_{51}, h_{27}, h_{29}, h_0, h_{52}, f_{168}, h_{33}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_4, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{f_{169}, h_{59}, h_{27}, h_{29}, h_0, f_{168}, h_{33}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_4, s_0, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{34}, h_{102}, f_{169}, h_{99}, h_{155}, h_{78}, h_{76}, h_{69}, h_{133}, f_{176}, h_{98}, h_{131}, f_{167}, h_{145}, h_{33}, h_{61}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{23}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{34}, h_{102}, f_{169}, h_{99}, h_{155}, h_{78}, h_{76}, h_{69}, f_{176}, h_{98}, f_{167}, h_{145}, h_{33}, h_{61}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{23}, s_{26}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{34}, h_{102}, f_{169}, h_{99}, h_{78}, h_{76}, h_{69}, f_{176}, h_{98}, f_{167}, h_{33}, h_{61}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{23}, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{102}, f_{169}, h_{99}, h_{69}, h_{33}, h_{61}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{23}, s_{26}, s_0, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{102}, f_{169}, h_{99}, h_{155}, h_{69}, h_{145}, h_{33}, h_{61}\}^{*(1)} \\
& \quad = \{s_{23}, s_{26}, s_8, s_5\}
\end{aligned}$$

7 APPENDIX

$$\begin{aligned}
& \{h_{17}, h_{46}, h_{150}, h_{11}, h_{155}, h_{80}, h_{76}, h_{27}, h_0, h_{44}, h_{47}, h_{45}, f_{167}, h_{25}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_2, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, h_{46}, h_{11}, h_{155}, h_{80}, h_{76}, h_{27}, h_{44}, h_{47}, f_{167}, h_{25}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_2, s_{26}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, h_{46}, h_{11}, h_{80}, h_{76}, h_{27}, h_{44}, h_{47}, f_{167}, h_{25}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_2, s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{11}, h_{80}, h_{44}, f_{167}, h_{25}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_2, s_{26}, s_0, s_{24}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, h_{46}, h_{11}, h_{80}, h_{76}, h_{27}, h_0, h_{44}, h_{47}, h_{45}, f_{167}, h_{25}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_2, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, h_{27}, h_0, h_{44}, f_{167}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_2, s_0, s_1, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{150}, h_{11}, h_{80}, h_{44}, f_{167}, h_{25}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_2, s_{24}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{155}, h_{27}, h_0, f_{168}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_2, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, f_{169}, h_{95}, h_{55}, h_0, f_{176}, h_{98}, f_{167}, h_{33}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_6, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, h_{91}, h_{88}, h_{34}, h_{102}, h_{54}, f_{169}, h_{46}, h_{59}, h_{67}, h_{95}, h_{101}, h_{55}, h_{11}, h_{99}, h_{73}, h_{74}, h_{155}, h_{80}, h_{122}, \\
& \quad h_{78}, h_{76}, h_{71}, h_{65}, h_{27}, h_{29}, h_{69}, f_{176}, h_{44}, h_{98}, h_{47}, f_{167}, h_{145}, h_{52}, h_{25}, f_{168}, h_{33}, h_{61}, f_{174}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{26}, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, h_{91}, h_{88}, h_{34}, h_{102}, h_{54}, f_{169}, h_{46}, h_{59}, h_{67}, h_{95}, h_{101}, h_{55}, h_{11}, h_{99}, h_{73}, h_{74}, h_{80}, h_{78}, \\
& \quad h_{76}, h_{71}, h_{65}, h_{27}, h_{29}, h_{69}, f_{176}, h_{44}, h_{98}, h_{47}, f_{167}, h_{52}, h_{25}, f_{168}, h_{33}, h_{61}, f_{174}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{26}, s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{102}, f_{169}, h_{59}, h_{67}, h_{99}, h_{27}, h_{29}, h_{69}, f_{168}, h_{33}, h_{61}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{26}, s_0, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{102}, f_{169}, h_{59}, h_{67}, h_{99}, h_{155}, h_{27}, h_{29}, h_{69}, h_{145}, f_{168}, h_{33}, h_{61}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_{26}, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, h_{91}, h_{88}, h_{34}, h_{102}, h_{54}, f_{169}, h_{46}, h_{59}, h_{67}, h_{95}, h_{101}, h_{55}, h_{51}, h_{11}, h_{99}, h_{73}, h_{74}, h_{80}, h_{78}, \\
& \quad h_{76}, h_{71}, h_{65}, h_{27}, h_{29}, h_{69}, h_0, f_{176}, h_{44}, h_{98}, h_{47}, h_{45}, f_{167}, h_{52}, h_{25}, f_{168}, h_{33}, h_{61}, f_{174}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_0, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{102}, f_{169}, h_{59}, h_{67}, h_{99}, h_{27}, h_{29}, h_{69}, h_0, f_{168}, h_{33}, h_{61}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_0, s_8, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{17}, h_{73}, h_{71}, h_{27}, h_0, h_{44}, f_{167}, f_{168}, f_{174}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_0, s_1, s_5\} \\
& \{h_{102}, f_{169}, h_{59}, h_{67}, h_{99}, h_{155}, h_{142}, h_{27}, h_{29}, h_{69}, h_0, h_{145}, f_{168}, h_{33}, h_{61}, f_{171}\}^{*(1)} \\
& = \{s_8, s_5\}
\end{aligned}$$

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